

Reflection Analytics in Educational Chatbot Rebo

A Field Study with Apprentices

Irmtraud Wolfbauer ^{a, b, c *} <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2973-9680>

Mia Magdalena Bangerl ^{a, b} <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9401-3106>

Amel Hamidovic ^b <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9941-374X>

Viktorija Pammer-Schindler ^{a, b} <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7061-8947>

^a Know-Center GmbH, Graz, Austria

^b Graz University of Technology, Austria

^c Private University College of Teacher Education Augustinum, Graz, Austria

corresponding author: Irmtraud Wolfbauer iwolfbauer@know-center.at

Abstract:

We investigate a conversational agent for reflection for apprentices (Rebo). To develop Rebo's adaptivity mechanism, we performed a feature analysis on 153 interactions with a non-adaptive version of the agent from previous work. We identified which linguistic features correlate with manual reflectivity coding in said dataset. Rooted in these reflection analytics, we implemented rules within Rebo to adapt its responses to learner statements, as well as provide feedback to the learner at the end of the interaction. We then conducted a 12-week field study with 19 apprentices who reflected with Rebo 130 times (1-14 interactions per apprentice). Rebo's feedback and our manual coding correspond (classifications "reflective", "partly reflective", and "non-reflective" correspond to manually coded reflectivity scores of 9.8, 8.6, and 6.0 out of 10 points), and reflectivity is improved by adaptive follow-up questions in 93 interactions. Throughout the field study, engagement of apprentices did not decline, evidenced by the stable levels of reflectivity reached in conversations with Rebo. Finally, reflection competence increased statistically significantly (pre/post comparison Wilcoxon test: $r=0.7537$, $z=-2.820$, $p<0.01$), which indicates that apprentices learned to reflect through interaction with Rebo.

Keywords: reflection analytics, educational chatbot, conversational agent, reflection guidance chatbot, apprentices

Acknowledgements:

We express our thanks to Katharina Maitz who co-supervised Amel Hamidovic's master thesis, which formed the basis for designing Rebo's adaptation mechanisms, and to Alfred Wertner who implemented Rebo.

1. Introduction

With this paper, we put forward the design and evaluation of an adaptive conversational agent that guides apprentices to reflect on their ongoing work practice: Rebo, the reflection guidance chatbot. Educational chatbot Rebo is deeply embedded in the target users' working and learning context, which is Austrian apprentices in technical fields, training at a workshop. Rebo's usage patterns and wording are tailored to the target audience, the agent's pedagogical concept and dialogue structure are based on research on learning through reflection. Our goal was to implement a reflection guidance tool that is target group appropriate for apprentices and eases them as learners into deeper thoughts, step by step, in order to help them improve their learning and their reflection skills. In prior field studies (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022), with a non-adaptive version of Rebo (dialogue structure with minor deviations and no adaptive agent responses), we found, firstly, that apprentices understand the dialogue structure and can lead coherent and reflective conversations with the non-adaptive Rebo (Wolfbauer et al. 2020). Secondly, when used over a time period of 12 weeks, apprentices' reflection competence significantly increased (pre/post comparison), and thirdly, that engagement with the non-adaptive Rebo decreased significantly within these 12 weeks (Wolfbauer et al. 2022). From a learning perspective, it is this last point that we address in the present work, namely, how reflectivity of repeated chatbot interactions with the conversational agent Rebo develops over time. From a technical perspective, we address the means applied to develop adaptivity based on analysing user turns in the conversation with the agent, i.e., reflection analytics within a computer-mediated reflective conversation: How accurate are Rebo's reflection analytics in comparison to manual coding?

Reflection analytics have already been identified as interesting and challenging in AIED (Cui et al. 2019; Kovanović et al. 2018; Ullmann 2017, 2019). Also, educational chatbots are studied within AIED (Khosrawi-Rad et al. 2022; Wollny et al. 2021) as part of a long tradition of adaptive learning systems. With this work, we contribute to the following themes relevant to AIED: adaptive learning systems, chatbot research and adaptation to user responses, teaching reflection as a learning strategy, professional learning focusing on apprentices. Specifically, we contribute by investigating an educational chatbot that embeds reflection analytics to provide adaptive responses to user statements.

For our work, we define reflection as an individual, metacognitive activity, where the learner reviews past experiences to learn from them. With this definition, we approach Schön's understanding of reflection-on-action (Schön 1983), which means that reflection takes place after a process is finished, with the goal to build knowledge and integrate skills. Boud et al. (1985) highlight the future-directedness of reflection, i.e. that it is important in reflection to move from revisiting past experiences towards thinking about the future. Furthermore, Boud et al. (ibid) stress the importance of deliberately attending to emotions experienced during an experience as part of the reflection process. All these aspects (revisiting – in our case a single – past experience, attending to emotions during the experience, and thinking about the future) are taken up in the design of our reflective agent's (Rebo's) dialogue structure. Pammer-Schindler and Prilla (2021) further highlight that the reflection object - the practice that is reflected on and that will be changed through reflection – motivates why people reflect. We have taken this up in designing the socio-technical embedding of Rebo, by ensuring that apprentices reflect on tasks that are important to their profession. Further, Pammer-Schindler and Prilla (ibid) discuss that it is desirable to consider how the reflection object is represented in a tool for reflection. In our work, we ask apprentices to (verbally and/or with pictures) document the experience they reflect on prior to conversing with the agent, in order to start from an explicitly represented experience.

Prior work has ascertained that prompts support reflection, in general finding that more directed prompts work better (Asano et al. 2015; Ifenthaler 2012; Kocielnik and Hsieh 2017b; Renner et al. 2016; Shin et al. 2018; Williams et al. 2016) and that prompting can be made adaptive (c. f. Fessl et al. 2017 for an overview on computer-mediated reflection prompts). While most prior work has investigated single prompts for reflection (e. g. Fessl et al. 2017), there is little work that investigates conversational reflection guidance, in which multiple reflection prompts follow-up on each other (Kocielnik et al. 2018b; Kocielnik and Hsieh 2018; Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022).

Apprentices are a unique target group for educational technology because they are situated both in educational learning and workplace learning settings. They are young people in educational contexts, learning in formal learning environments when they are at vocational school, yet they are workers at their factories,

learning in informal learning environments for the most part of their time (Wolfbauer et al. 2020). In this combination of workplace learning and structured lessons, reflection is a key mechanism for turning insights gained from various sources into integrated knowledge (Schwendimann et al. 2015). Reflection improves learning experiences and outcomes (Cattaneo and Motta 2021) as well as constitutes an essential skill for self-regulated learning (Pintrich 2000; Zimmerman 2000), which means that the motivation to learn and the direction for learning activities is determined by the learners themselves (Winne 2005). In the light of changing professional requirements and lifelong professional learning, self-regulated learning and reflection are important skills for apprentices' future careers. Reflection skills are also considered a key factor in organisational learning (Burnes et al. 2003; Fuller and Unwin 2003; Rainbird et al. 2004). It is important that apprentices contribute to organisational learning. In their position as young team members and learners, they contribute bottom-up to organisational learning based on their learning experiences and reflection (Knipfer et al. 2013; Prilla et al. 2013). Consequently, acquiring reflection skills is not only beneficial to the apprentices themselves but also in the best interest of their current and future employers.

This paper is structured as follows: We first describe background and related work on AI for reflection and reflection analytics (Section 2). Secondly, we outline the research questions asked in this work (Section 3). We then describe design and socio-technical embedding of the conversational agent Rebo (Section 4), with special focus on reflection analytics for conversational agents (Section 5). Subsequently, we describe the field study that was conducted to evaluate the agent and answer our research questions, and how we analysed our data (Section 6). Eventually, we present our results (Section 7) and discuss our findings and insights (Section 8).

2. Background and Related Work

2.1. AI for Reflection

Adaptive technologies that tailor reflection triggers to specific users and user groups have proved successful for fostering and guiding reflection in multiple studies (Ghajargar et al. 2018). There are various roles technologies can take in reflection (Fleck and Fitzpatrick 2010; Krogstie et al. 2013). They range from capturing relevant data, triggering users to reflect e.g., via reminders or other functionalities, giving access to information relevant for reflection, supporting sharing of experiences and reflection outcomes, up to structuring the reflection process itself (Krogstie et al. 2012; Slovák et al. 2017).

2.1.1. Adaptive prompts for reflection

Prompting, most often accomplished through questions or sentence starters, is a common approach to engage learners in reflection (Fessl et al. 2016). Previous research has explored the effectiveness of single reflection prompts compared to a control condition without prompts (Ifenthaler 2012; Renner et al. 2016) with the result that well-tailored prompts are fruitful to learning. Furthermore, the impact of different prompt designs or wordings has been investigated (Kocielnik and Hsieh 2017b) and it has been shown that specificity of wording and detailed reflection instructions yields better results. In contrast, our current work focuses on studying a more complex dialogue structure with a sequence of interconnected reflection prompts that follow-up on each other. For example, Kocielnik and Hsieh (2017a) presented users with their Fitbit data and asked tailored reflective questions to help them gain insights related to their fitness and personal goals. Similarly, the studies in Fessl et al. (2017) involved presenting users with their work-related data and prompting them to provide targeted explanations, such as their mood in specific work situations or their time management, enabling reflection within the context of their workplace. We draw from these studies that reflective questions are most effective when they are specifically targeted to the user as well as the reflection goal they are aiming for. In this work, the goal of reflection is to enhance a learning experience by thinking it through on multiple levels that have been shown to benefit reflection.

2.1.2. Conversational agents

Expanding one prompt to a series of consecutive prompts in form of a natural communicative interaction with an agent is a valid approach for numerous reasons. Firstly, from the perspective of human-computer interaction, the impression of talking to a person comes more natural to people and when multiple prompts are strung together in a conversation, it does not overwhelm learners (c. f. Knights 1985). Secondly, attending to multiple aspects of a reflection object as suggested by learning sciences (Boud et al. 1985; Pintrich 2000;

Zimmerman 2000) is easier when the consecutive steps are embedded into a conversational flow. Consecutive prompts offer the additional benefit of providing users with feedback in their role as learners (Aleven et al. 2017). Conversational agents can adapt comments, follow-up questions, and the direction the interaction takes to user input.

Conversational agents, or chatbots, have become omnipresent in all walks of life. From facilitating searching in FAQ databases (e. g. Han et al. 2023) over learning companions (e. g. Ruan et al. 2021) to mental health (e. g. Gabrielli et al. 2020) and grief counselling (Xygykou et al. 2023), the areas of application are manifold and expanding. Conversational agents take on a multitude of roles in interactions, from teaching and motivational agents over peer agents, to teachable agents, with numerous nuances (cf. Kuhail et al. 2023). The target audiences for chatbot design have also expanded with time. There are agents specifically targeted towards young children, such as Dapie (Lee et al. 2023) and Elinor (Xu et al. 2022), and Sriwisathiyakun and Dhamanitayakul have designed an agent with the aim to enhance digital literacy in senior citizens (2022).

The first significant steps in conversational user interfaces were made in the mid-1960s by Weizenbaum with an agent that emulated a psychotherapist, ELIZA (Weizenbaum 1966). Only 4 years later, Carbonell designed the SCHOLAR tutor, a first leap towards the use of adaptive conversational agents in AIED in the shape of a computer-assisted instruction (CAI) dialogue between a student and the agent (Carbonell 1970).

The history of adaptive conversational agents in AIED is rooted in intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), spearheaded by Graesser, VanLehn, Rosé et al. with the design of AutoTutor (Graesser et al. 2001). Auto tutor has been shown to help learners acquire knowledge of computer literacy and physics and has led the authors to the insight that “conversational dialogue substantially improves learning.” (p 50). Based on this insight that the conversational interaction paradigm has a positive effect on learning, further research on conversational agents for learning was inspired. GuruTutor (Olney et al. 2012) builds on AutoTutor, yet, models its instructions after expert tutors as opposed to the non-expert strategies AutoTutor emulates. Gaze Tutor (D’Mello et al. 2012) extends GuruTutor with an eye-tracking camera to monitor students’ engagement and react if students’ gaze patterns indicate that they zoned out. D’Mello et al. (2010) have furthermore explored the role emotions play in learning, which is also an essential part of successful reflection as defined in this work. Based on their insights, the agent version Affective AutoTutor (D’Mello and Graesser 2012) was implemented to display empathy with appropriate discourse moves and facial expressions.

A different focus was set by McNamara et al. with iSTART (McNamara et al. 2006), an ITS for adolescents to train reading strategies. WritingPAL (Roscoe et al. 2014) is an ITS that teaches writing strategies to teenagers. In contrast to the aforementioned systems, it engages students with features such as game-based practice and automated feedback but without a conversational agent. The acquisition of self-regulated learning skills, similar to the focus on reflection skills in the work presented here, is the objective of MetaTutor (Azevedo et al. 2010). This agent has also been extended by an affective learning companion that takes the learner’s affective state into consideration, measured by sensors and based on previous interactions with the system (VanLehn et al. 2014). Self-regulated learning as well as reflection is a meta-competence for successful learning. Similarly, DeepTutor (Nye et al. 2014; Rus et al. 2015) trains problem-solving activities in order to promote deep learning.

In this context of human-computer interaction and learning, numerous further conversational agents have been shown to foster the acquisition of factual knowledge, for example, QuizBot (Ruan et al. 2019), Sara the lecturer (Winkler et al. 2020), and MathBot (Cai et al. 2019). Furthermore, they moderate group discussions to facilitate collaborative learning based on collaboration scripts (Adamson et al. 2014), and improve collaborative problem solving skills (D’Mello et al. 2024). They assist learners in language acquisition, for, example with EnglishBot (Ruan et al. 2021), and the agent ImpactBot helps researchers to create impact statements for projects or papers in a critical way (Mukherjee et al. 2023). PairBuddy (Robe and Kuttal 2022), an example for a different agent role, is a conversational agent that helps to learn programming skills by taking on the persona of a fellow learner for pair programming. More recent studies have investigated conversational agents that support users in developing argumentation skills (Le et al. 2018; Mirzababaei and Pammer-Schindler 2021, 2024; Rakshit et al. 2019; Wambsganss et al. 2021), or in improving their problem solving skills by dividing goals into subgoals with a logic tutor (Shabrina et al. 2023). Danry et al. (2023) promote critical thinking in users by AI-framed questioning instead of AI explanations, thus allowing users to actively construct knowledge and discern logical problems. Conversational agents specifically for reflection, however, have not been widely

studied: Kocielnik et al. have investigated conversational reflection guidance in relationship to achieving set fitness goals (Kocielnik et al. 2018b), and for reflecting on time management (Kocielnik et al. 2018a), the latter work with a focus on comparing input technologies (speech vs. textual).

Human behaviour traits, such as arguing over a topic or displaying humour, have been shown to have an engaging effect on learners in chatbot interactions (Ceha et al. 2021; Nijholt 2007). Learners appreciate conversational agents that display humour, to the point that it can improve learning outcomes (Ceha et al. 2021). Recent studies on the effects of emotional expressiveness of chatbots even explore the effects of the tone of voice in which a chatbot delivers a message (Zhu et al. 2022). Introducing these characteristics of interactions between humans into chatbot interactions can create more natural interaction experiences (Nijholt 2007).

In this span of over 20 years of adaptive tutoring with conversational agents, which developments can we perceive? Striking progress was made on a technical level, especially recently with the evolution of large language models and conversational agents like OpenAI's ChatGPT. Educational chatbots emerge that build on ChatGPT and control its output with elaborate prompts (e. g. Lee et al. 2023). AIED research on chatbots has investigated numerous agent roles and combinations of different agents within the same interaction, as well as explored target audiences and learning scenarios. We can observe a tendency from emulating a typical human teacher or tutor towards targeting users and groups of users with their very specific needs and interests, and tailoring learning content specifically to individual learning situations. It is however noteworthy that throughout the progresses made and despite the success of chatbot interventions, learning with humans is still the guiding principle that most researchers set their sights on.

In own prior work we have developed the dialogue structure of the reflection guidance agent Rebo that we investigate in this work (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022). In contrast to the agents described above, we attempted to structure the way learners think about their learning experiences. The dialogue structure consists of a sequence of reflective questions that ask the user to take different perspectives regarding their working and learning experience, framed with a greeting and a goodbye. These perspectives are rooted in the learning sciences, and the phrasing of the reflective questions was co-designed with apprenticeship supervisors (see Section 3.2 for details). Further, we have investigated how Rebo works as part of apprentices' work and learning practice (socio-technical embedding – Wolfbauer et al., 2022, see Section 3.1 for details). However, in this prior work, the agent was non-adaptive. This means that its responses did not change depending on user statements. Despite this, we found that conversations between the non-adaptive Rebo and apprentices were mostly coherent (97% in Wolfbauer et al. 2020, 100% in Wolfbauer et al. 2022) and reflective (87% of interactions reached reflection stage 'learning or change' in Wolfbauer et al. 2020; average reflectivity of chatbot interactions was 7.3 out of 8 points in Wolfbauer et al. 2022). Furthermore, we found that apprentices significantly increased their reflection competence (Wolfbauer et al. 2022). We conducted a field study where 14 apprentices used the non-adaptive Rebo 108 times (7.7 interactions per apprentice on average). A pre/post comparison of the apprentices' reflection competence, evidenced by an unguided reflective essay writing task, showed a statistically significant increase (Average reflectivity of first essay $M=2.4$ ($SD=2.1$) and average reflectivity of final essay $M=5.9$ ($SD=1.2$), paired samples t-test $t_{11}=4.89$, $p<.001$). However, there was a significant drop of reflectivity over time in interactions with the non-adaptive Rebo, shown with a paired-samples t-test from interaction one ($M=7.77$, $SD=.44$; $n=13$) to interaction eight ($M=7.00$, $SD=1.12$; $n=9$) ($t_7=2.50$, $p=.041$; $n=8$). In this work, we follow-up by asking whether we can avoid this drop and maintain learner engagement by adding adaptivity to the conversational agent. Note that we are keeping the same dialogue structure as in own prior work.

2.2. Reflection analytics

Reflection analytics aims to determine whether and to what extent reflective thinking has taken place, mostly based on textual features. Work on reflection analytics based on written text has been of interest to educational technology for a considerable amount of time. There are two streams of research. First, computational linguistics, that analyses texts by the correlation of linguistic features with manual coding. Second, approaches incorporating machine learning methods, where similar procedures are implemented with strong usage of machine learning to learn classifications.

Computational linguistics are used in studies on reflection analytics in various contexts and can be combined with other approaches. Approaches include manual coding based on content analysis employed to detect reflection in journals of nurses (Wong et al. 1995). Ullmann (2017) worked on automated detection of reflection elements and assigned lists of keywords to specific categories of reflection. Subsequently, a reflective writing framework (RWF) was developed that categorises students' writings into reflective and non-reflective (Alrashidi et al. 2020). Kovanovic et al. (2018) employed the "Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count" (LIWC) (Pennebaker et al. 1999) tool and Coh-Metrix (McNamara et al. 2014) to understand and categorise students' reflective writings. The LIWC tool was also used in subsequent studies, for example by Jung and Wise (2020) in the context of health professions education, and by Cui et al. (2019) for students in dental education. The latter evaluated reflective writings by mapping textual features onto reflection elements distilled from literature on reflective learning. Zhang et al. employed a mixed-methods approach to evaluate reflective writing in the context of teacher education. They combined qualitative content analysis with computational linguistics and BERTopic (Grootendorst 2022) to show that different evaluation methods reveal different aspects of reflection indicators (Zhang et al. 2023).

Several recent studies employ machine learning algorithms to assess the quality of written reflections. Ullmann (2019) investigated the applicability of machine learning methods on automated reflection analytics and found it to be a promising approach. Building on his insights, and on the aforementioned reflective writing framework (RWF), Alrashidi et al. developed an ITS model incorporating automated reflection analytics (2023). Other research in this area employs machine learning-based regression techniques (i.e., random forest, support vector machine, multi-layer perceptron) to assess reflection depth of reflections written during game-based learning by middle school students (Carpenter et al. 2020). Barthakur et al. (2022) assess professionals' reflective writing in the context of workplace learning in a MOOC using machine learning classification. Solopova et al. developed PapagAI (2023), a system for automated assessment of reflection quality and depth, detection of emotions and sentiment as well as topics to provide automated feedback.

In this work, we focus on the works in computational linguistics by Wong et al. (1995), Ullmann (2017), Kovanovic et al. (2018), and Cui et al. (2019) because they seemed most applicable to our data and research setting. We describe their works in more detail below.

Wong et al. (1995) performed content analyses of reflective journals of nurses, complemented by interviews to understand their thought processes. This formed the basis of a coding procedure to determine the degree of reflection of a written piece of work. To ensure coding reliability, five coders were involved in establishing and checking the content analysis codes. Two levels of coding were used. The first level involved examining entire reports for evidence of "elements of the reflection process" as described by Boud, Keogh, and Walker (1985). The second level categorized students according to the model of Mezirow et al. (1990) as "non-reflector": lacking any evidence of reflective thinking, "reflector": showing evidence of reflective thinking but lacking critical change of perspective, or "critical reflector": showing features of a reflector and showing change of perspective. The reliability coefficient for the second level of coding was 0.88, indicating a high level of agreement among the coders. Applying the reliability formula to the first level of coding was more challenging due to difficulties in identifying and allocating paragraphs within extensive reports. Based on their results, Wong et al. (ibid) concluded that presence or absence of reflection in (student) writings can be reliably determined by allocating into the three categories of non-reflector, reflector, and critical reflector. However identifying specific textual elements within journals and allocating them to the finer levels of reflection from Boud, Keogh, and Walker (1985) was less reliable.

Due to the high effort needed for manual coding and analysis of reflective thinking in writings, Ullmann (2017) proposed an architecture for automated detection of reflection elements. The architecture consists of three annotators: the first one annotates logical thinking and argumentation, thus phrases which are related to premise and conclusion starting with "because", "hence", "therefore" and others by using regular expressions. The second one annotates self-questioning as open questions which is considered to indicate reflective thinking, again by using regular expression matchers. The third one annotates keywords semantically related to reflection according to the WordNet lexical database (Princeton University 2010). The framework yielded reliable and promising results for detection of reflection elements but did not give any indication about the depth of reflection. Therefore, Ullmann (2017) examined how specific keywords could indicate one or more of

eight depth levels or “categories of reflection”: Reflection, Experience, Feeling, Belief, Difficulty, Perspective, Learning and Intention. The assignment to any of these categories was done by majority agreement of eight coders. A subset of the British Academic Written English (BAWE) corpus was used as a dataset. The data was divided into training, validation, and test sets, and a keyword selection process was performed using log-likelihood ratio on the training and validation sets to determine the best candidate keywords. The keywords were then evaluated on the test set to measure accuracy and inter-rater reliability using Cohen's κ (Cohen 1960) with results ranging from 67% to 93% accuracy and κ values ranging from 0.28 to 0.65, indicating moderate to substantial agreement. Keywords appearing in at least 50% of the folds were reported. The evaluation of this study demonstrated that by using word lists, categories of reflective writing can be detected with fair to good reliability, outperforming chance agreement. (Although some categories such as 'Perspective' and 'Learning' were more challenging to detect compared to 'Experience', 'Reflection', and 'Feeling'.) This gave reason to believe that the level of reflectivity in conversations could also be determined using word lists.

Kovanovic et al. (2018) developed a classification system to categorize students' reflections based on an existing coding scheme (Robert L. Hulsman and Jane van der Vloedt 2015). The classification achieved 89% accuracy and a Cohen's κ of 0.51, indicating a moderate agreement above chance levels. The use of linguistic metrics from the tools “Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count” (LIWC) (Pennebaker et al. 1999) and Coh-Metrix (McNamara et al. 2014) showed potential for understanding students' reflective writings and different psychological processes. Secondly, they evaluated linguistic features of different types of student reflection and found that e.g., the use of perceptual words (e.g., seen, view, saw) and the complexity of causal expressions (ratio of causal particles to causal verbs) were significant reflection predictors. Additionally, they observed that highly theorized linguistic metrics from LIWC and Coh-Metrics analysis tools provided more value than basic N-gram features. An application of the metrics of the Coh-Metrics tool to reflection analytics of reflective dialogues seems promising.

Cui, Wise, and Allen (2019) created a framework for aligning high-level reflection qualities with automatically extractable low-level text features based on reflective writings from health education. They acquired reflective statements through a custom online reflection system from post-graduate students in dental education at the end of every year over a period of four years. Their approach was to empirically analyse textual features with tools such as LIWC by Lin et al. (Lin et al. 2016; Mauroux et al. 2014) and map the suitable ones onto “reflection elements” from Boud, Keogh, and Walker (Boud et al. 1985) and Gibbs (Gibbs 1988): “Description”, “Analysis”, “Feelings”, “Perspective”, “Evaluation” and “Outcome”. They concluded that “Reflection analytics built on the kinds of features explored in this study can provide students with feedback on missing elements of reflection and recommendations for what they can do to improve their self-regulation” and how it could support self-regulated learning through retrospection and adjustment of learning strategies. They emphasized that while online learning environments generate valuable data for studying reflection, there is a lack of appropriate tools, theories, and frameworks in analytics to provide useful insights. We conclude that implementing reflectivity detection and instantaneous feedback into the conversational agent guiding reflection can improve reflection outcomes for learners.

All these studies on reflection analytics work with reflection texts in essay form, most of them written in English. This raises two questions: Firstly, how will these approaches work for German texts? Secondly, all these studies have been carried out in the context of interaction paradigms other than a conversational agent. By this we mean, that in related work on reflection analytics, the result of the reflection analytics has been given visually in relationship to the longer text but not in the form of a conversational agent or conversational interface. There is very little prior work on conversational agents for reflection (to the best of our knowledge only work by Kocielnik, Hsieh et al. discussed in subsection 2.1); and none of it uses reflection analytics to drive the adaptive response to user statements within the conversation. Subsequently, the second question is whether the same procedures of analysing reflection work in the context of conversations, which can be expected to be less elaborate and more dynamic.

Research Questions

Considering the above discussed literature, we ask the following research questions in the here presented field study:

RQ1 Accuracy of reflection analytics: How accurate are Rebo's in-built reflection analytics in comparison to manual reflectivity coding?

RQ2 Improvement of reflectivity within chatbot interactions: How is reflectivity of single interactions between Rebo and the apprentices' improved (comparison between two subsequent turns of the apprentice, before and after an adaptive response)?

RQ3 Development of interactions over time (engagement): How does reflectivity of repeated chatbot interactions with the conversational agent Rebo develop over time?

RQ4 Reflection competence: How does apprentices' reflection competence change when compared pre/post the field study?

RQ1 follows upon extensive work on reflection analytics. While we assume that reflection analytics can work, the challenge is how accurate they can be in the face of much shorter texts, consisting of utterances of one party of a dialogue. RQ2 evaluates the immediate effect of reflection analytics within an ongoing chatbot interaction. RQ3 and RQ4 extend previous studies on static conversational agents (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022) that showed increased reflection competence in learners over time, yet decreased reflectivity in repeated chatbot interactions.

3. Conceptual Design of Rebo

In this section, we describe the conceptual design of Rebo as a socio-technical intervention.

3.1. Socio-technical Design and Embedding of Rebo

The reflective conversational agent Rebo that we investigate in this work is not isolated from the field setting in which it is used, and the way it is used within this setting. We call this the socio-technical design and embedding of Rebo, highlighting our understanding that by inserting Rebo into a field setting we are actually changing the socio-technical system in this setting. On the other hand, the results of our study are not just results regarding Rebo as a technological artifact but results regarding the socio-technical design and embedding of Rebo. This is no limitation, rather it is natural for a learning tool that in order to achieve its goal (=to support learning), it has to be accessible and usable in the destined environment as well as have meaning in the learner's world and learning journey.

The setting of our field study is a training workshop for apprentices in metal technology, mechatronics, and electrical engineering. In this training workshop, apprentices are given practical learning tasks that are relevant in the work practice they are training for. These tasks are designed by dedicated apprenticeship trainers to match the apprentices' skill level and the training's learning objectives. They are mainly manual, hands-on activities that are fitting to the apprentices' level of expertise. For the purposes of this field study, apprentices additionally had to document each learning task digitally and upload this description onto an online learning environment. With the upload, we implemented Rebo to pop up, greet the apprentice by name, and the apprentices were instructed to partake in the reflective conversation with Rebo. Thereby, the reflection happens after a learning task (reflection-on-action according to Schön 1983). This point in time was identified as a suitable moment for reflection in consultation with the apprentices' trainers because apprentices at this time 1) are at their laptops and 2) have time to reflect before starting another activity. Also, the wording of the chatbot's turns was discussed with the apprentices' trainers.

The design rationale for verbalising Rebo's subsequent turns was to make the agent's tone fit the setting of apprenticeship. Throughout a sequence of field studies (Prior study 1: Wolfbauer et al., 2020; prior study 2: Wolfbauer et al., 2022) we slightly changed wordings where we received feedback directly from trainers or by analysing interaction log data that the wording might have been off or misleading. This did not result in a change of the conceptual dialogue structure (reflection script, see Section 3.2). In order to develop Rebo's verbalisations as well as when the agent would be used, we carried out a number of pilot studies with users other than the participants of the field study we present in this paper. See **Fig. 1** for an overview in which the blue parts constitute the pilot studies.

Fig. 1 Timeline of evaluation process of Rebo: The pilot studies are highlighted blue, and the main study is highlighted green.

3.2. Dialogue structure and reflection aspects

The dialogue structure of Rebo follows a reflection script, by which we mean a conceptual dialogue structure that defines the sequence of aspects that apprentices are asked to consider in reflection (see Table 1). This script needs to be instantiated by concrete verbalisations in Rebo's subsequent turns. The script itself was used in preceding field studies (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022) with slightly different verbalisations. It takes up prior work that highlights that reflection means to revisit past experience and think about what happened (Steps 0-1), attend to emotions, analyse the past experience, and direct thoughts to the future (Steps 2-5) (Boud et al. 1985; Schön 1983). Within Rebo, this reflection script is embedded in a chatbot interaction which starts with a greeting and ends with a summative (adaptive) feedback of the agent and a goodbye. Furthermore, Rebo implements the following adaptive turns: Rebo reacts with empathy to user statements, and with follow-up questions based on reflection analytics (details on the adaptation mechanisms in Section 4). See **Fig. 2** for an example interaction between Rebo and an apprentice.

Table 1: Reflection script (conceptual dialogue structure) within Rebo.

Reflection Aspect	Description
0 Revisit	Returning to the learning experience, definition of the reflection topic
1 Description	Description of the work task that is reflected on as learning opportunity
2 Judgement	Evaluation of outcomes and explanation of self-assessment
3 Emotions	Attending to emotions experienced while performing the task
4 Learning	Evaluating the learning experience, gathering insights
5 Planning	Potential behaviour changes in the future

Fig. 2 An apprentice reflects with Rebo on a work experience - Example interaction with adaptive turns and feedback comment calculated at runtime (categorised as reflective, based on the on-the-fly calculation of the Reflectivity_score, see Section 4.3.1)

4. Adaptation Mechanisms in Rebo

In this section, we explain how we developed the adaptive mechanisms of Rebo: follow-up questions when apprentices did not reflect on a specific aspect of the learning experience, empathy, requests for elaboration, summative feedback. Their development is based on data gathered in two 3-month trials of the non-adaptive precursor version of Rebo (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022). We first explain what data was gathered and how we coded it for the reflection analytics (5.1). We then analysed the data with computational means (reflection analytics) with the goal to identify linguistic markers that correlate with reflectivity in our dataset. In the context of our reflection guidance chatbot Rebo, such reflection analytics would be the basis for adaptivity. An open question at the start of our investigation was whether the linguistic markers found in our dataset would correspond to those found in prior work (Cui et al. 2019; Kovanović et al. 2018; Ullmann 2017, 2019). We use two tools for our feature analysis to identify relevant linguistic markers, namely Coh-Metrix 3.0 (McNamara et al. 2014) and RATTE (Wild and Pissarek 2016), following plausibility checks based on literature and three distinctive interactions that were then excluded from the final dataset. We consequently outline the adaptivity mechanisms we implemented in Rebo as a result of our analysis (see Section 4.3).

4.1. Data collection, coding, and pre-processing.

Before developing Rebo as described in this paper, we evaluated a non-adaptive version of the agent in two 12-week field studies (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022). The dialogue structure of the agent in these field studies (reflection script) is the same as Rebo's dialogue structure. Apprentices also used the non-adaptive precursor version in the same manner, i.e., apprentices reflected on practical learning tasks assigned by their apprenticeship supervisors as part of their training. We used data from the first field study, consisting of 153 chatbot interactions by 18 apprentices (Wolfbauer et al. 2020), for the feature analysis. For Rebo's heuristics, we additionally used the data from the second field study with 14 first-year apprentices, consisting of 108 chatbot interactions (Wolfbauer et al. 2022).

The interactions with the non-adaptive Rebo of the first field study were coded for coherence, reflectivity, and user engagement. Reflectivity was coded according to the levels of reflection defined by Prilla and Renner (2014):

1. Provision and description of experience
2. Reflection on experiences, including analysis and potential solutions
3. Learning or change

All 153 interactions reached reflection level 1, as apprentices had to submit a description of the learning task before proceeding to the conversational reflection with the non-adaptive Rebo. Reflection level 2 was reached by 114 interactions and level 3 was reached by 133 interactions. These findings from Wolfbauer et al. (2020) constitute the baseline for the feature analysis described in this paper: the manual coding of the interactions serves as gold standard to assess computationally assessed linguistic markers regarding their suitability to indicate reflectivity.

We first pulled three distinctive interactions out of the pool of 153 chatbot interactions to conceptually discuss linguistic features described in prior reflection analytics work (Cui et al. 2019; Kovanović et al. 2018; Ullmann 2017, 2019). The remaining 150 interactions were used in further feature analysis. As the data was in German and often included typos, Austrian slang words, and abbreviations, it was necessary to pre-process the dataset for automated analysis. Typos were corrected, Austrian slang words were replaced with their standard form, and only abbreviations without equivalent were retained for the dataset that was analysed with RATTE. Prior work on reflection analytics is mainly for English texts, therefore, we also created an English version of our data set to be able to use Coh-Metrix for a feature analysis. To prepare our data for this tool, the interactions were translated automatically using the Google Translate API V2. A manual check of all 150 interactions was performed to ensure translation accuracy, and minor errors were corrected. Note that we excluded the agent's turns from analysis because we were interested in reflectivity in the learner's replies, not the agent's questions and statements.

In order to perform statistical analyses on the features, all interactions of the dataset were categorized into four groups based on a binary pattern, corresponding to the coded reflection levels described above:

- Descriptive Group 00, where no level of reflection is reached (apart from level 1, which was reached before the chatbot interaction)
- Partly reflective Group 10, which reached reflection level 2
- Partly reflective Group 01, which reached reflection level 3
- Highly reflective Group 11, which reached both level 2 and level 3

Out of the 150 analysed chatbot interactions, 10 interactions were classified into the descriptive Group 00, 7 interactions in the partly reflective Group 10, 25 interactions in the partly reflective Group 01, and 108 interactions in the "highly reflective" Group 11.

4.2. Reflection Analytics

The dataset of 150 chatbot interactions was computationally analysed with the web version of Coh-Metrix 3.0 (McNamara et al. 2014) in English and with the RATTE language tool (Wild and Pissarek 2016) in German. Coh-Metrix is a computational language tool that analyses texts considering an extensive set of linguistic markers. RATTE is a language tool that originally aims at categorising texts according to their complexity and suitability for different reading levels, but it also allows usage of only single features.

Our goal was to identify linguistic markers that correlate with the manually coded reflectivity in our dataset (Groups 00-11). To determine the usefulness of a feature in providing information about reflectivity, two minimum requirements were set: due to the imbalance in category size (group 00: 10 interactions, group 10: 7 interactions, group 01: 25 interactions, group 11: 108 interactions), we were looking for features that differentiate Group 00 (no level of reflection reached) from Group 11 (all levels of reflection reached). Further, due to the small size of our dataset, we required a feature to be conceptually plausible as an indicator for reflection. Therefore, we started with a theoretical examination of available features to identify features as potentially relevant reflection indicators beforehand. A homogeneity test was conducted on all the features to

determine the appropriate statistical analysis procedure for further examination. An ANOVA and a post-hoc pairwise comparison using Hochberg's GT2 test were conducted on features with homogeneous variances, while a Welch-Test and Games-Howell post-hoc test were applied to features with heterogeneous variances to check significant group differences.

We started our analysis with the translated dataset and the Coh-Metrix 3.0 online tool. The results showed that the variances of 34 metrics were homogeneous whereas 75 metrics had heterogeneous variances. Out of the metrics with homogeneous variances, nine differed significantly between the four groups according to the results of the ANOVA. Of these, five could distinguish between the least reflective and most reflective groups: DESSLd (the standard deviation of the mean sentence lengths), DESWLtd (the standard deviation of mean word lengths), DRVP (the incidence score of verb phrases), WRDVERB (the incidence score of verbs), WRDPRO (the number of personal pronouns per 1000 words). Out of the 75 metrics with heterogeneous variances, 14 yielded a significant Welch-Test result, indicating significant differences between the groups. Out of these, six distinguished between Group 00 and Group 11: DESWC (the word count metric), DESSL (the sentence count metric), LDMTLD (the measure of textual lexical diversity), SMCAUSvp (the causal verbs and causal particles incidence), SYNLE (the mean number of words before the main verb), WRDAOAc (the mean age of acquisition). Overall, this results in 11 out of 105 metrics of Coh-Metrix that we identified as potentially useful reflection indicators for our dataset. For detailed results, please consult Appendices A.1. Feature Analysis with Coh-Metrix and A.2. CohMetrix linguistic markers – ANOVA Values.

The quantitative analysis yielded the following results for every metric of RATTE: Out of 23 provided metrics by the tool, seven had homogeneous variances, and five out of these were significant according to the ANOVA: gSmog, Disyllables, Lexical Density, Filler Words and the readability index LIX. Inspecting the 16 metrics with heterogeneous variances six yielded a significant Welch-Test result: RIX (Regensburger Index describing textual complexity and returning the appropriate reading age of a text in school grades), Word Count, Average Sentence Length, Types, Monosyllables and Trisyllables. In sum, out of 23 measurements from RATTE, eight fulfil the set requirements to be useful as reflection indicators for conversations (in German Language). For detailed results, please consult Appendices A.3 Feature Analysis with RATTE and A.4 RATTE linguistic markers – ANOVA Values.

When we compare our findings to previous studies on elaborated texts (Cui et al. 2019; Kovanović et al. 2018; Ullmann 2017, 2019), we see a difference in reflectivity indicators between conversations and essays. Reflection indicating measures for texts which were examined in previous works were only partially applicable to conversations. From the Coh-Metrix features proposed by Cui et al. (2019) and Kovanovic et al. (2018), only four were relevant for further examination namely: SYNLE, SMCAUSvp, SMINTER and CNCAII. Of these, only the first two proved useful as reflection indicators for conversations in our data. At the same time, reflection indicating measurements that are relevant to conversations were disregarded for elaborated texts. This indicates that the discrepancy between conversations and texts are not negligible, and reflection indicators cannot be used interchangeably without adjustment. Descriptive word count and sentence length measurements emerged as crucial linguistic indicators for identifying reflective thinking in guided conversational reflections, regardless of the language-specific tools used.

We eventually decided on RATTE as the fitting tool for our data for two reasons. Firstly, it directly analyses the source language, thereby avoiding language-specific deviations. Secondly, the metrics of the tool provide a higher coverage (34.7% RATTE vs. 10.2% Coh-Metrix), thereby providing more reliable measurements.

4.3. Adaptive Features Implemented in Rebo

4.3.1. Implemented automated reflection analytics and feedback

Following the analysis described in 4.2, we extended Rebo with the publicly available JAR library of RATTE (Wild and Pissarek 2016) to acquire text features from the German interactions. We selected the features that our analysis identified as the main indicators of reflectivity in chatbot interactions: the number of trisyllables ($p < 0.1$), the number of monosyllables ($p < 0.05$), wordcount ($p=0.00$), and the Regensburger Index RIX that describes textual complexity and returns the appropriate reading age of a text in school grades ($p=0.00$). We did not include the word types - indicator, due to missing documentation of the measurement and the lack of traceability of its computation. The summative (adaptive) feedback of the agent at the end of each interaction

(see Section 3.2) is based on these linguistic features, whereby RIX is used as the primary reflection indicator. It is computed as follows: a “Reflection_score” is computed (see formula below), and thresholds as shown in Table 2 are applied to select one of three feedback comments.

$$\text{Reflection_score} = \text{RIX} * 100 + \text{number of words} + \text{number of monosyllables} + \text{number of trisyllables}.$$

The Reflection_score was defined to give the RIX value (which also contains the average sentence length) greater weight and relevance compared to the other values that express absolute frequencies; thus, it was multiplied by 100.

Based on the correlation between mean RIX values and the reached reflection levels (1.156 for Group 00 – non-reflective, 1.698 and 1.6771 for Group 01 and Group 10 – partly reflective, and 2.370 for Group 11 – reflective), score thresholds were estimated. The calculation was adapted after several manual tests and the piloting phase.

Table 2: Selection of Rebo's feedback comment based on the Reflection_score

Reflection_score	Categorisation	Rebo's feedback comment	Example interaction
> 300	reflective	“I think this talk was really cool! I'm glad that you do your best :D”	See Fig. 2
Between 200 and 300	partly reflective	“I think this talk was alright :)”	See Fig. 3 : blue interaction on the left Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.
< 200	non-reflective	“I think this talk was not that great, you could make more of an effort next time.”	See Fig. 3 : green interaction on the right

Example interaction categorised as partly reflective	Example interaction categorised as non- reflective
Hello Francis	Hi Jan
hello	Greetings
Which task are we talking about today?	What task are we talking about today?
exercise 5	Sanding exercise
Go on and tell: What was it you did for this task? Step by step...	Please describe how you performed this work
I made a sketch, then a description of the function, and eventually the fine-drawing, computer drawing and the construction are done.	I filed, then I drilled, and I sanded
How well does your solution fit the task you were given?	How well does your solution fit the task you were given?
very well	Well
That's not enough information for me, please explain this a bit more thorough!	That's not enough information for me, please explain this a bit more thorough!
everything worked very well	Well
What did you like best about it?	What did you like best about it?
The construction because I really liked it	Nothing
Way to go :D	Please explain this a bit better.
What would you say have you learned from this work?	No
Not much because the exercises are very similar	That's a pity :/
Wat will you do better next time?	Why didn't you like it?
Nothing because everything worked the way I did it	I did like it
If you performed the exact same task again tomorrow, what would you do differently?	What did you learn from this work?
Absolutely nothing	Sanding
I enjoyed talking to you :)	Some more details if you please ;)
me too	No
I think this talk was alright :)	If you performed the exact same task again tomorrow, what would you do differently?
See you next time ;)	Nothing
see you soon	Nothing
	OK, thanks for joining this chat :)
	You're welcome
	I think this talk was not that great, you could make more of an effort next time.
	Have a nice day and see you soon!

Fig. 3 Example interactions of apprentices with Rebo that were categorised as partly reflective and non-reflective, based on the on-the-fly calculation of the Reflectivity_score.

Based on the result of the feature analysis that showed that the number of words is an important reflection indicator, we also implemented a word count interceptor mechanism. We heuristically determined a threshold of five words as minimum word count for each answer to a reflection trigger. In case an apprentice answers with five words or less, Rebo follows-up with a request to be more elaborate.

4.3.2. Heuristics to select specific branches and steer the interaction

We implemented further heuristics based on qualitative analysis of the two prior field studies (Wolfbauer et al. 2020; Wolfbauer et al. 2022). We identified keywords that constitute generally accepted answers in their context, where we found it difficult to determine whether actual thought processes had taken place or whether they had just showed desired behaviour. For example, “paying attention to measurements” and “being precise” are general directions typically given by trainers, and it was decided to meet these statements with follow-up questions to elicit more specificity (e.g., “Which techniques could you apply to make your measures more exact?”). Another example is that apprentices, when asked to judge the outcomes of their work, sometimes responded with elaboration on how much of an effort they made. Here, Rebo should react positively and encouragingly, but ask again how well their result fits the task at hand (e.g., “You did your best, that’s great! Did you also complete your work according to the specifications?”). Altogether, we implemented 10 heuristics rules on the 4 reflection aspects Judgement, Emotions, Learning and Planning (see Appendix B for the full list). We consider such heuristics an important part of socio-technical design, as they take up specifics of the socio-technical system into which our intervention is placed.

5. Field Study Method

For the evaluation of the conversational agent Rebo and to answer our research question on how well AI works in the field, we conducted a 12-week field study examining the effects of repeated chatbot interactions in the target user group over a longer period of time.

5.1. Study Procedure

Our field study lasted for 12 weeks. The first and last reflections during the study were different. To assess the apprentice's reflection competence before and after the period of repeated interactions with Rebo, we asked them to write a reflective essay instead of chatting with Rebo (hereafter referred to as Essay 1 and Essay 2). This method of testing reflection competence has proved valid in previous work (Wolfbauer et al. 2022) and is founded in research on reflective writing (Kovanović et al. 2018; Ullmann 2017, 2019; Wild and Pissarek 2016). So, with uploading the finished work task, a text window popped up with only these instructions and no further help or feedback:

*Thank you for your submission!
Think carefully about your work and explain what you learned from this task. Write a text with your reflection in the field.*

The 12 weeks of repeated chatbot interactions were framed by two workshops, one at the beginning and one at the end of the field study. The initial workshop was held to introduce the apprentices to their e-learning platform and showed them where to find their learning sources and how to upload their work. They were informed about the field study they took part in, that we were developing a reflection guidance chatbot for apprentices and that their interactions and feedback would help us improve it. We also discussed the benefits of reflecting on working experiences. They filled in a survey on self-regulated learning skills (Wolfbauer 2023), they uploaded their first work task (that was finished the day before) and wrote Essay 1. The workshop at the end of the study was accordingly used to upload the final work task and write Essay 2, to create a similar writing situation. Furthermore, we collected direct feedback from the apprentices as well as their supervisors and asked them to fill in the feedback survey and the survey on self-regulated learning for the second time. For an overview of the evaluative processes, see the "main study" highlighted in green in **Fig. 1**.

5.2. Data collection

Four different data sources were used within the study: 1) the interactions between the apprentices and Rebo, 2) two reflective essays, written by the apprentices at the beginning and at the end of the main study, 3) a survey on self-regulated learning strategies, filled out by the apprentices at the beginning and at the end of the main study, and 4) a feedback-questionnaire filled out by the apprentices at the end of the main study, as well as direct and spontaneous feedback from the apprentices.

The **interactions between the apprentices and the chatbot Rebo** provide the base data to answer the first three research questions. The interactions enabled the analysis of the reflection analytics and the calculation of the reflection scores per interaction, based on the coding of the interactions by the research team. Thus, the chatbot-apprentice interactions provide the necessary measures to answer Research Question 1 – Accuracy of reflection analytics, Research Question 2 – Improvement of reflectivity within chatbot interactions, and Research Question 3 – Development of interactions over time.

The **reflective essays written by the apprentices** at the beginning and the end of the main study were collected to measure the reflection competence of the apprentices before and after the period of regular interactions with the chatbot. The comparison of the essays' reflection scores provides insights into the effect of the chatbot intervention on the reflection competencies of the apprentices, thus answering Research Question 4 – Reflection competence.

The **repeated survey on self-regulated learning** filled out by the apprentices at the beginning and the end of the main study was conducted to gain insights into their self-described learning and reflection practices, and how these opinions have changed before and after the chatbot intervention. The questionnaire (Wolfbauer 2023) was adapted and translated from Duncan et al.'s (Duncan et al. 2015) "Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire", and was collected to provide a broader answer to Research Question 4 – Reflection competence.

Finally, the **feedback questionnaire** filled out by the apprentices at the end of the main study was conducted to understand the apprentices' subjective experiences during the main study (e.g., how they perceived the chatbot, if they thought they improved their reflection skills). Therefore, the questionnaire data also contributes to answering Research Question 4 – Reflection competence.

5.3. Participants

Our sample includes 19 first-year apprentices who were training at the above-described workshop for three months. We started the study with 21 apprentices but two of them terminated their training during the field study. Typically, apprenticeship in Austria is started after 9 years of school. Accordingly, the average age of our participants is 15.9 years; we have two apprentices in our sample who started later than the others, one at 17, one at 21 years of age. Apprentices in our cohort train at seven different companies and in nine different jobs, all situated around the areas of metal technology, electrical engineering, and plastics engineering. 11% of apprentices in our cohort are female and 89% are male, which is a representative gender distribution for these fields, since 81% of Austrian apprentices in “trades and crafts” are male (WKO 2021).

All 19 apprentices interacted with the chatbot Rebo, however, the exact number of uses varied, with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 14 interactions per apprentice (MD=5, SD=4.3). For our pre- and post-tests, the number of participants is slightly lower. The two essays to assess reflection competence were written by 14 apprentices and the feedback questionnaire was filled in by 15 apprentices.

5.4. Data analysis

5.4.1. Chatbot interactions

The interactions between the apprentices and chatbot Rebo were systematically coded by applying a five-perspective coding system, based on the reflection script underlying Rebo’s dialogue (Section 3.2). The five perspectives; description, judgement, emotions, learning, and planning; were coded in 3 coding levels (0-2 points). In sum, 10 reflectivity points could be achieved per interaction. For each perspective, a coding of zero points was given when an apprentice did not write anything in the interaction dialogue concerning the given perspective. One point was given when an apprentice wrote something concerning the given perspective but did not explain or concretize the thought. Finally, two points were given when an apprentice wrote something concerning the given perspective that was concrete and well-explained. An overview of the coding scheme with exemplary data is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Coding system for reflective essays and chatbot interactions

Points	Description	Examples: reflection perspective “emotions”, translated from original	
		CHATBOT INTERACTIONS (Rebo, Apprentice)	ESSAYS (Apprentice)
0	level not achieved	R: How did you feel while doing this work? A: How do you think I felt? Like I adored milling?	[missing]
1	level achieved, activity is identifiable on the desired level	R: How did you feel while doing this work? A: Good.	It was a really hard task to design and build something on our own, but it was not so bad to build it then.
2	level well achieved, thought process on desired level is comprehensible and relevant	R: How did you feel while doing this work A: It was fun because you had to think about it a bit to solve the task.	We worked together as a team, and I really liked that everyone did what they do best and that we finished on time even though it was a big project.

The coding was carried out by two coders who first independently assessed the data based on the coding system. After the individual coding, points were compared. Since coding aimed to support evaluation, differences in coding were discussed until consensus was reached. A score sum representing overall reflectivity (hereafter referred to as reflectivity score) was then calculated for each interaction from the points of the five perspectives.

Coherence of the interactions between the chatbot and the apprentices was assessed as a semantic property of the resulting reflection dialogues, following van Dijk (1977), on a 3-level coding system described in Table 4.

Table 4: Coding system for coherence of chatbot-apprentice interactions

Points	Description	Example (short extract) (translated from German)
0	Interaction is incoherent, makes no sense as a dialogue	[didn't occur in the data]
1	Interaction has some problems on single branches but for the most part, it makes sense	C: Are you happy with the result of your work? Why / why not? A: I'm happy because it went well, and I hardly made any mistakes. C: Oh no! What was the problem? A: I had almost no problems.
2	Interaction is coherent, questions, answers, and follow-up questions make sense and fit	C: How well does your result fulfil the set task? A: I think well but I didn't fully finish. C: What was the problem? A: Too little time, and I didn't always have an available workstation.

Because the number of chatbot interactions varied greatly between the 19 apprentices, only descriptive indicators such as measures of central tendency, and distributions were used to analyse the data.

In order to elicit how accurate Rebo's adaptive features are and how adaptive follow-up-questions improve reflectivity on the level of individual interactions, all adaptive turns were coded for accuracy of trigger, appropriateness of Rebo's turn, and influence on reflectivity of the interaction. Each dialogue step attending to a different reflection aspect was coded twice. We first coded the initial user response, that would have been the only response in a static dialogue structure and, in case it triggered a follow-up prompt, coded the second response as well. Thereby we can document the differences in reflectivity achieved between a non-adaptive and an adaptive conversational agent. Finally, Rebo's feedback comment based on reflection analytics at the end of the interaction is compared to the manually coded overall reflectivity score of the interaction, in order to test its accuracy.

5.4.2. Reflective essays

The reflective essays that the apprentices wrote without chatbot guidance to test their reflection competence were also coded and assessed based on the coding schema introduced in 5.4.1. Again, the same two coders first separately assessed each reflective essay, then values were compared and discussed in case of point differences until a consensus was reached. Both the individual perspective points (representing the different reflection aspects) and the overall reflectivity score (maximum 10 points – maximum two points for each of the five perspectives) were calculated. Additionally, the wordcount of each essay was noted and compared. Correlations between the wordcount and the number of addressed perspectives (number of perspectives with scores > 0) were calculated for each essay. Due to the non-parametric data distribution, Wilcoxon signed rank tests were calculated for the overall reflectivity score, the reflectivity score of each perspective, and the wordcount between the two essays.

5.4.3. Self-regulated learning questionnaire

The results of the repeated-measures self-directed learning questionnaire were analysed descriptively. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between pre- and post-intervention data.

5.4.4. Feedback questionnaire

The results of the feedback questionnaire were analysed descriptively, by calculating percentages, means, and standard deviations. Answers to open questions were summarized.

6. Results

6.1. Accuracy of reflection analytics

In this section, we analyse the results with respect to RQ1 – Accuracy of reflection analytics. We answer this question by analysing all adaptive turns taken by the agent.

6.1.1. Rebo's adaptive turns

In the main study, 19 apprentices reflected with Rebo in a total of 130 interactions. The coherence of the interactions of the apprentices with Rebo was 2 out of 2 points for 112 (86.15%) out of the total 130 interactions. In 18 interactions (13.85%), coherence was coded with 1 out of 2 points. None of the apprentice-chatbot-interactions was coded with zero points for coherence. In those conversations that were coded with only 1 point for coherence, the underlying problems were either problems with the agent (faulty adaptivity, 8 out of 18) or disengagement of the apprentice (10 out of 18).

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. provides an overview of all adaptive turns taken by the agent. We indicate for each adaptive statement: how often they were triggered accurately and how often they were triggered falsely. In absolute frequencies, there were 484 adaptive turns (statements and follow-up questions) taken by the agent; 383 triggered correctly and 101 triggered falsely, according to the coding scheme. We furthermore present how Rebo's adaptive turns performed focusing on the apprentices' individual learning experiences. We calculated for each apprentice how accurate Rebo's adaptive turns were. In the table, we outline how many apprentices were affected by each adaptive branch, and how many apprentices had interactions where the classification was correct and where it was false. The number of triggers per apprentice varies according to the high variance in numbers of interactions across participants, yet there were adaptive turns triggered in each apprentices' reflections (per apprentice: mean=22.16, min=2, max=47). Please note that the classification of triggers is within our coding system. When reflection on a given answer of the user is coded as 2, triggering an adaptive follow-up question is coded as false, even if it does not disturb the conversational flow or improves the outcome. (Please see Appendix B - Heuristics and rules implemented in Rebo - for the complete dialogue flow.)

Table 5: Rebo's adaptive turns (in 130 interactions): Frequency of trigger and accuracy in absolute numbers as well as numbers of apprentices that were affected.

Heuristic	Triggered how many times in absolute frequencies (in 130 interactions)			How many apprentices were affected? (0 - 19)		
	Altogether	Accurately	Falsely	Altogether	Accurately	Falsely
Reflection perspective: Description						
missing elaboration	7	7	.	6	6	-
Reflection perspective: Judgement						
positive judgement	36	36	-	14	14	-
negative judgement	31	21	10	13	12	7
fake judgement	-	-	-	-	-	-
missing elaboration	38	38	-	16	16	-
Reflection perspective: Emotions						
positive emotions	56	56	-	18	18	-
negative emotions	12	9	3	9	7	3
yes emotions	5	5	-	3	3	-
no emotions	21	2	19	12	2	12
missing elaboration	24	24	-	16	16	-
Reflection perspective: Learning						
learning recognised	41	40	1	17	16	1
yes learning	1	1	-	1	1	-
no learning	1	-	1	1	-	1
negative learning	20	2	18	9	2	7
fake learning -learning	-	-	-	-	-	-
fake learning - knowledge	-	-	-	-	-	-
missing elaboration	33	32	1	14	14	1
Reflection perspective: Planning						

planning recognised	48	47	1	16	16	1
no planning	66	19	47	18	11	14
fake planning - precision	-	-	-	-	-	-
fake planning - measuring	-	-	-	-	-	-
missing elaboration	43	43	-	16	16	-
Total	484 (100%)	383 (79.13 %)	101 (20.87 %)			

6.1.2. Rebo's feedback at the end of the interaction

In this section we evaluate the summative feedback that Rebo gives at the end of each interaction. Rebo gives feedback in three categories: 1: reflective, 2: partly reflective, 3: non-reflective. We correlate this automatically determined feedback category with the manually coded overall reflectivity score. In 17 of 130 interactions, the chat was closed before Rebo's feedback comment. Checking back with apprentices where that had happened, we found out that Rebo's last turn was misinterpreted as the end of the interaction. In 94 interactions, stage 1 feedback was given, in 16 interactions stage 2 feedback, and in 2 interactions stage 3. The interactions that got the best feedback (1: reflective) were manually coded with reflectivity scores of mostly 9 and 10 points, and one with 8 points, with an average of 9.8 points. The interactions with negative feedback (3: non-reflective) were manually coded with a reflectivity score of 5 and 7 points, average of 6 points. The medium feedback (2: partly reflective) was a bit more diverse, including interactions with reflectivity scores from 6 to 10 points, averaging on 8.6 points.

6.2. Improvement of reflectivity within chatbot interactions

In this section, we analyse the results with respect to RQ2 – Improvement of reflectivity within chatbot interactions. We answer this question by examining the reflectivity scores that were achieved in the chatbot-apprentice interactions, in line with the coding system introduced in section 5.4.1. We analyse to what extent the adaptive follow-up questions asked by the chatbot in response to an apprentice's previous turn improved the reflectivity of the interaction.

Table 6 illustrates which adaptive turns of the agent resulted in improvement of reflectivity within and beyond the coding scheme. When reflectivity was improved beyond our coding scheme (meaning the apprentice's response contained new insights regarding the given reflection perspective, despite already having achieved 2/2 points with their initial turn), it is noted but not further classified. Rebo's follow-up questions led to improvement within our coding scheme in 20% of cases and to improvement beyond the coding scheme in 40% of cases when we consider the single interactions. Table 6 also provides information on how useful Rebo's adaptive follow-up questions were for the individual learners. It outlines to what extent the quality of the apprentices' reflections profited on average by Rebo's adaptive features.

Table 6: Rebo's adaptive follow-up questions: improvement of reflectivity with regard to the applied coding scheme in absolute numbers

Heuristic	Improvement of reflectivity by Rebo's follow-up questions		
	Improved within coding scheme	Improved beyond coding scheme	No improvement
Missing elaboration (sum over all reflection aspects)	37	38	71
Negative judgement	2	23	6
Fake judgement	-	-	-
Yes emotions	5	-	-
no emotions	2	10	9
yes learning	1	-	-
no learning	-	1	-

negative learning	1	12	7
fake learning -learning	-	-	-
fake learning - knowledge	-	-	-
no planning	11	31	24
fake planning - precision	-	-	-
fake planning - measuring	-	-	-
Total	59 (20.27%)	115 (39.52%)	117 (40.21%)

Table 7 shows that reflectivity was improved on all 5 reflection aspects. From the 60 cases of improvements within the coding scheme, the triggered new response changed coding from “not achieved” to “well achieved” (0 points -> 2 points) in 6 cases, and from “achieved” to “well achieved” (1 point -> 2 points) in 54 cases.

Table 7: Improvement of reflectivity on single reflection aspects by Rebo's adaptive turns

Number of improvements of the given reflection aspect by Rebo's adaptive follow-up questions					
Improvement level	1 - Description	2 - Judgement	3 - Emotions	4 - Learning	5 - Planning
1 point -> 2 points	2	20	11	7	14
0 points -> 2 points	0	1	1	1	3

Finally, to gauge the benefit of Rebo's adaptive turns in terms of improving reflectivity of user answers, we calculate the average reflectivity achieved in interactions as well as per apprentice (for the apprentices' reflectivity scores, see also Table 8). By coding reflectivity on each level before and after the adaptive responses, we found that average reflectivity without adaptivity in the agent would be lower in both cases. The average reflectivity score of the 130 interactions is 9.62 out of 10 points (M=10 points, SD=0.88 points). Without adaptive turns of the agent, this average reflectivity score would be 9.11 instead. When we focus on the learning experiences of each apprentice, their average reflectivity score was 9.35 out of 10 points. Without adaptivity in the agent, the average reflectivity per apprentice would be 8.59 points.

6.3. Development of interactions over time

In this section, we analyse the results with respect to RQ3 - Development of interactions over time. We answer this question by analysing the overall reflectivity score (maximum 10 points – maximum 2 points for each of the five perspectives, see Section 5.4.1) for each apprentice over time.

Table 8 shows the overall reflectivity scores of each apprentice's interactions with Rebo, as well as each apprentice's average reflectivity score throughout the field study. The table visualises that the number of interactions vary greatly between the 19 apprentices, and how the quality of the guided chatbot interactions stay high for the bulk of the cohort throughout repeated interactions. The reflectivity scores of most apprentices consistently stay between 8 and 10 points and do not drop over time, with only two apprentices scoring below 8 points. Out of the two apprentices with lower points (compared to the rest of the sample), one apprentice only reflected once, and the other one reflected five times with the chatbot. All other apprentices' reflectivity scores consistently stayed between 8 and 10 points and had reflectivity score means of ≥ 9.00 . Six apprentices consistently achieved 10 points in all their interactions. Overall, the apprentices' interactions with the chatbot achieved very high reflectivity scores consistently and without decrease throughout the field study.

Table 8: Overall reflectivity scores of apprentices (A, B, ..., S) per interaction (reflection chat) with Rebo, ordered by overall number of interactions (I1, I2, ..., I14).

Overall reflectivity scores of every Rebo interaction per apprentices		
Apprentice	Interaction number	Average reflectivity

	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12	I13	I14	scores per apprentice
A	5														5,00
B	8	10													9,00
C	10	10	10												10,00
D	10	10	10												10,00
E	10	9	9												9,33
F	10	10	10	10											10,00
G	10	10	10	9											9,75
H	10	10	10	10											10,00
I	9	8	5	7	6										7,00
J	10	9	10	10	9										9,60
K	10	9	8	10	10	10	10								9,57
L	9	10	10	10	10	10	10								9,86
M	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10							10,00
N	10	9	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	9					9,70
O	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10					10,00
P	10	10	10	10	10	9	9	10	10	10	10	10	10		9,85
Q	9	10	10	10	10	10	8	10	9	8	10	9	10		9,46
R	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	9,93
S	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	9	10	9	9	10	9	9	9,57

As an example, Fig. 4 shows the development of apprentice “K”’s reflectivity score from their first interaction with the chatbot to their seventh and last interaction. Apprentice “K” consistently achieved between 8 and 10 reflectivity points per interaction, with no downward tendency towards the end.

Fig. 4 Development of one apprentice's reflectivity score

6.4. Reflection competence

In this section, we analyse the results in respect with RQ4 – reflection competence. To answer this question, we analyse the reflection essays written by the apprentices as pre- and post-tests of their reflection competence. We compare the mean reflectivity scores of the two essays written by the apprentices at the beginning and end of the field study with repeated chatbot intervention, in line with the coding system described in section 5.4.2. Furthermore, we consider the results of the repeated self-regulated learning questionnaire and the feedback questionnaire to understand apprentices’ subjective experiences with the chatbot intervention, their opinions on their own reflection competence, and their progress throughout the field study.

6.4.1. Reflective Essays

For the reflective essays, the Wilcoxon signed rank tests showed significant differences in median between the 14 first essays, before the chatbot intervention, and the 14 second essays, after the chatbot intervention. These indicate an improvement in the overall reflectivity score, the reflection aspect description, and the wordcount of the essays.

The overall reflectivity score resulted in a strong and highly significant improvement between the 14 Essays 1 and the 14 Essays 2, based on the Wilcoxon test result of $r = 0.7537$ ($z = -2.820$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$). The means improved from 2.07 points in Essays 1 ($MD=2$, $SD=0.83$) to 4.21 points in Essays 2 ($MD=4$, $SD=2.39$).

The median word count increases from 38 words in Essays 1 ($M=46.36$, $SD=37.82$) to 78 words in Essays 2 ($M=110.43$, $SD=91.54$). Though standard deviations indicate a high fluctuation in wordcount between participants, the Wilcoxon test result still shows a strong improvement effect of $r = 0.7801$ ($z = -2.919$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$) between the two essays.

For the perspective “description”, apprentices mean points improved from 0.57 points at the first essays ($SD=0.94$, $MD=0$) to 1.57 points at the second essays ($SD=0.63$, $MD=2$). The Wilcoxon test results show an effect size of $r = 0.7056$ ($z = -2.640$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$), which indicates a strong improvement in points between the two essays (according to Cohen 2013). For the perspectives judgement, emotions, learning and planning, the Wilcoxon test produced no significant test results, though the means were always higher in Essay 2, as compared to Essay 1. The perspective planning was not present in any of the Essays 1 and scored 0.29 on average in Essays 2, see **Fig. 5**.

Fig. 5 Mean reflectivity scores per perspective for Essays 1 and Essays 2

The apprentices also improved on the number of reflection perspectives that they addressed in their essays. The mean for Essays 1 was 1.07 perspectives addressed ($MD=1$, $SD=0.47$), while the mean for Essays 2 was higher, at 1.44 perspectives addressed ($M=2$, $SD=1.44$).

6.4.2. Self-regulated learning questionnaire

The results of the questionnaire data were inconclusive. Most question scales had unsatisfactory Cronbach's alpha results (Cronbach 1951), indicating problems with internal consistency and scale reliability. Distributions between individual items from the pre- and post-intervention questionnaire varied strongly, and they did not indicate any overall trend (neither positive nor negative) or substantial significant correlations. Due to these results, the validity of the answers cannot be assured, and individual results will not be further included.

6.4.3. Feedback survey

The results of the feedback questionnaire indicate that the apprentices themselves think that they have learned to reflect better after the chatbot intervention, and that this development is mainly due to reflecting with chatbot Rebo. As visible in **Fig. 6**, mean agreements to the statements “I have learned what is part of a reflection by interaction with Rebo, and used this knowledge in my essay”, “I know better now, what reflection is.”, and “This essay was easier to write than the first one” are above 4 (of the maximum agreement 5), with the median = 4 for all three items, and a standard deviation < 0.6 for all three items.

Fig. 6 Feedback on self-perceived reflection skills in relation to Rebo

Furthermore, as visible in Fig. 7, 73% of the n = 15 questioned apprentices think that they can reflect better at the end of the field study, and that the reason for that is Rebo.

Fig. 7 Apprentices' perceived main reason for improved reflection competence is chats with Rebo

7. Discussion and Conclusion

We consider the adaptation mechanisms built into Rebo as satisfactory on the grounds of two pieces of evidence. Firstly, due to the results of evaluating their accuracy, we see merit in Rebo's heuristics as well as the immediate feedback to the learner based on reflection analytics. Secondly, the analysis of follow-up answers after Rebo's adaptive turns shows significant improvement of reflectivity. The applied setting in which we have come to these insights has its merits as well as its limitations. The number of participants (19) and the overall number of interactions (153) are small and pose a limitation to our results. Accordingly, options for statistical analysis were also limited. However, we present results of a full cohort that interacted with this learning tool over 12 weeks, which was the entire timespan of their training period at a workshop. There was no kind of selection or bias in our participants because it was the whole group.

Concerning the accuracy of Rebo's adaptive turns, empathetic statements were triggered correctly in 97 % of cases, and adaptive follow-up questions were triggered correctly in 67 % of cases. The built-in, instantaneous feedback to the reflection chat with Rebo at the end of each interaction has yielded results that are similar to the expert coding. We interpret these findings as indication that Rebo's heuristics worked, and that the textual features picked for analysis with RATTE are relevant indicators of reflection. The approach to compute these features and provide immediate feedback to learners has merit and should be further pursued.

Concerning the improvement of reflectivity by adaptive turns, we have seen those adaptive turns, though technically not perfect, serve to improve the apprentice's answers on 115 occasions and concerning all five reflection aspects (21 % improvement within our coding scheme, 40 % improvement beyond our coding scheme). As a pointer towards future research, we note that we have also detected a ceiling effect in our coding scheme, meaning that it is not differentiated enough to capture all improvements. We therefore highlight that both for our own future work and others, a more differentiated coding scheme should be considered, keeping in mind the potential downside that more "grades" per aspect might also lower the inter-rater reliability.

Furthermore, we have seen that throughout the 12 weeks of this study, there was no drop of apprentices' engagement with Rebo, as evidenced by consistently high reflectivity scores (cp. Section 7.3). While this in itself is encouraging, we especially highlight that this is new and relevant in comparison to own prior results: In Wolfbauer et al. (2022) we have described a field study with apprentices (different cohort, similar demographic characteristics, same field setting) who used a non-adaptive prior version of Rebo throughout 12 weeks. There, we found that apprentices' engagement dropped significantly after eight interactions. Besides improving apprentices' answers within a single interaction (after a follow-up question, apprentices mostly gave better answers), the adaptation mechanisms built into Rebo therefore help to keep up the engagement of apprentices with the intervention.

Finally, consistent with said own prior work (Wolfbauer et al., *ibid*), we found that apprentices' reflection competence increased. We measured a strong and highly significant rise in reflection competence in our respondents after 12 weeks of repeated chatbot interactions. There were improvements in every reflection aspect the dialogue attends to, the planning aspect was not reflected on at all in the first essays and present in the second ones. This further underlines the learning effect repeated chatbot interactions have on learners. Even though the significant improvement in reflectivity from Essay 1 to Essay 2 indicates a positive effect of the chatbot in unguided reflections, it should still be considered that the mean reflectivity scores are low for both essays in comparison to the chatbot interactions. The maximum number of points per essay or interaction is 10 (2 points for each of the five reflection aspects). The average reflectivity score for Essay 2 is only 4.21 points, in contrast to Rebo interactions with an average reflectivity score of 9.62 points. The question that remains to be answered is, how much the reflection competence of our respondents could improve if the study were to be prolonged. It might eventually reach a point where the curve flattens and increase of reflection competence would stagnate, yet we can see no indication that this point has already been reached in our field study. Following studies with longer periods of training accompanied by chatbot-guided reflections could investigate the learning curve of people improving their reflection skills with a reflection guidance chatbot, by conducting a longer field study with regular assessments.

The reflection dialogues between apprentices and Rebo are highly interesting in their diversity despite the rigid dialogue structure. As mentioned before, our results concerning improvement of reflectivity could not be entirely captured by the here applied coding scheme. One way to approach this issue would be refinements in the quantitative coding scheme. Considering the richness of the interaction data, we believe that it would be promising to take a qualitative approach. For example, qualitative content analysis has already been shown to yield insightful results with similar data by Wolfbauer et al. (2023). Dialogues of this nature could furthermore provide insights into learning processes with chatbots and learners' attitudes towards AI. A (critical) discourse analysis could also focus on how learners construct identities of their self and the agent, a non-human interlocutor, in such dialogical reflection interactions (c. p. Heritage 2010).

We can overall conclude that implementing reflection analytics in a conversational agent with the here described approaches yields promising results and should be further pursued and optimised. The overall success and acceptance of the reflection guidance chatbot implies that reflective learning on practical work tasks guided by a conversational agent is a valid approach to reflective learning guidance. Accompanying evaluations also indicate sustainable positive effects on the apprentices' self-regulated learning, especially their reflection skills. The adaptation mechanisms based on reflection analytics of previous findings with a non-adaptive agent prove suitable to foster deeper reflection in the learner. Also, the reflection analytics of the ongoing chatbot interaction to provide instantaneous feedback have proved largely accurate. In contrast to previous work, the implementation of adaptive turns results in maintaining high reflectivity of reflection chats throughout repeated interactions with the agent.

References

- Adamson D, Dyke G, Rosé C (2014) Towards an Agile Approach to Adapting Dynamic Collaboration Support to Student Needs. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*:92–124
- Aleven V, McLaughlin EA, Glenn RA, Koedinger KR (2017) Instruction based on adaptive learning technologies. In: R. E. Mayer & P. Alexander (ed) *Handbook of research on learning and instruction*, 2nd edn. Routledge, New York, pp 522–560
- Alrashidi H, Joy M, Ullmann TD, Almujaally N (2020) Educators' Validation on a Reflective Writing Framework (RWF) for Assessing Reflective Writing in Computer Science Education. In: Kumar V, Troussas C (eds) *Intelligent Tutoring Systems: 16th International Conference, ITS 2020, Athens, Greece, June 8–12, 2020, Proceedings*, 1st edn., vol 12149. Springer International Publishing; Imprint Springer, Cham, pp 316–322
- Alrashidi H, Almujaally N, Kadhum M, Daniel Ullmann T, Joy M (2023) Evaluating an Automated Analysis Using Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing Approaches to Classify Computer Science Students' Reflective Writing. In: Ranganathan G, Bestak R, Fernando X (eds) *Pervasive Computing and Social Networking*. Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, pp 463–477
- Asano Y, Dutta M, Thakur T, Solyst J, Cristea S, Jovic H, Petersen A, Williams JJ (2015) Exploring Additional Personalized Support While Attempting Exercise Problems in Online Learning Platforms. In: Meinel C, Pérez-Sanagustín M, Specht M, Ogan A (eds) *Proceedings of the Eighth ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 235–238
- Azevedo R, Johnson A, Chauncey A, Burkett C (2010) Self-regulated Learning with MetaTutor: Advancing the Science of Learning with MetaCognitive Tools. In: Khine MS, Saleh IM (eds) *New science of learning: Cognition, computers and collaboration in education*. Springer, New York, NY, Heidelberg, pp 225–247
- Barthakur A, Joksimovic S, Kovanovic V, Mello RF, Taylor M, Richey M, Pardo A (2022) Understanding Depth of Reflective Writing in Workplace Learning Assessments Using Machine Learning Classification. *IEEE Trans. Learning Technol.* 15:567–578. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2022.3162546>
- Boud D, Keogh R, Walker D (eds) (1985) *Reflection: Turning experience into learning*, London, New York
- Burnes B, Cooper C, West P (2003) Organisational learning: the new management paradigm? *Management Decision* 41:452–464. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00251740310479304>
- Cai W, Grossman J, Lin Z, Sheng H, Tian J, Wei Z, Williams JJ, Goel S (2019) MathBot: A Personalized Conversational Agent for Learning Math
- Carbonell J (1970) AI in CAI: An Artificial-Intelligence Approach to Computer-Assisted Instruction. *IEEE Trans. Man Mach. Syst.* 11:190–202. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMMS.1970.299942>
- Carpenter D, Geden M, Rowe J, Azevedo R, Lester J (2020) Automated Analysis of Middle School Students' Written Reflections During Game-Based Learning. In: Bittencourt II, Cukurova M, Muldner K, Luckin R, Millán E (eds) *Artificial Intelligence in Education: 21st International Conference, AIED 2020, Ifrane, Morocco, July 6–10, 2020, Proceedings, Part I*, 1st edn., vol 12163. Springer International Publishing; Imprint Springer, Cham, pp 67–78
- Cattaneo AAP, Motta E (2021) "I Reflect, Therefore I Am... a Good Professional". On the Relationship between Reflection-on-Action, Reflection-in-Action and Professional Performance in Vocational Education. *Vocations and Learning* 14:185–204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-020-09259-9>
- Ceha J, Lee KJ, Nilsen E, Goh J, Law E (2021) Can a Humorous Conversational Agent Enhance Learning Experience and Outcomes? In: Kitamura Y, Quigley A, Isbister K, Igarashi T, Bjørn P, Drucker S (eds) *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–14
- Cohen J (1960) A Coefficient of Agreement for Nominal Scales. *Educational and Psychological Measurement* 20:37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316446002000104>
- Cohen J (2013) *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. Routledge
- Cronbach LJ (1951) Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika* 16:297–334. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02310555>
- Cui Y, Wise AF, Allen KL (2019) Developing reflection analytics for health professions education: A multi-dimensional framework to align critical concepts with data features. *Computers in Human Behavior* 100:305–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.02.019>
- D'Mello S, Graesser A (2012) Emotions during Learning with AutoTutor. In: Durlach PJ, Lesgold AM (eds) *Adaptive Technologies for Training and Education*. Cambridge University Press, pp 117–139

- D'Mello SK, Lehman B, Person N (2010) Monitoring affect states during effortful problem solving activities. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 20:361–389
- D'Mello SK, Duran N, Michaels A, Stewart AEB (2024) Improving collaborative problem-solving skills via automated feedback and scaffolding: a quasi-experimental study with CPSCoach 2.0. *User Model User-Adap Inter*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11257-023-09387-6>
- Danry V, Pataranutaporn P, Mao Y, Maes P (2023) Don't Just Tell Me, Ask Me: AI Systems that Intelligently Frame Explanations as Questions Improve Human Logical Discernment Accuracy over Causal AI explanations. In: Schmidt A, Väänänen K, Goyal T, Kristensson PO, Peters A, Mueller S, Williamson JR, Wilson ML (eds) *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–13
- D'Mello S, Olney A, Williams C, Hays P (2012) Gaze tutor: A gaze-reactive intelligent tutoring system. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 70:377–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2012.01.004>
- Fessl A, Blunk O, Prilla M, Pammer V (2016) The Known Universe of Reflection Guidance: a Literature Review. *International Journal on Technology Enhanced Learning* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTEL.2017.10005148>
- Fessl A, Wesiak G, Rivera-Pelayo V, Feyertag S, Pammer V (2017) In-App Reflection Guidance: Lessons Learned Across Four Field Trials at the Workplace. *IEEE Trans. Learning Technol.* 10:488–501. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2017.2708097>
- Fleck R, Fitzpatrick G (2010) Reflecting on reflection. In: Brereton M (ed) *Proceedings of the 22nd Conference of the Computer-Human Interaction Special Interest Group of Australia on Computer-Human Interaction*. ACM, New York, NY, pp 216–223
- Fuller A, Unwin L (2003) Fostering Workplace Learning: Looking through the Lens of Apprenticeship. *European Educational Research Journal* 2:41–55. <https://doi.org/10.2304/eeerj.2003.2.1.9>
- Gabrielli S, Rizzi S, Carbone S, Donisi V (2020) A Chatbot-Based Coaching Intervention for Adolescents to Promote Life Skills: Pilot Study. *JMIR Hum Factors* 7:e16762. <https://doi.org/10.2196/16762>
- Ghajargar M, Wiberg M, Stolterman E (2018) Designing IoT Systems that Support Reflective Thinking: A Relational Approach. In: *International Journal of Design*, 12, vol 12, pp 21–35
- Gibbs G (1988) *Learning by doing: A guide to teaching and learning methods*. Further Education Unit
- Graesser AC, VanLehn K, Rose CP, Jordan PW, Harter D (2001) Intelligent Tutoring Systems with Conversational Dialogue. *AI magazine* 22:39 ff
- Han S, Liu M, Pan Z, Cai Y, Shao P (2023) Making FAQ Chatbots More Inclusive: An Examination of Non-Native English Users' Interactions with New Technology in Massive Open Online Courses. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 33:752–780. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-022-00311-4>
- Heritage J (2010) *Talk in Action: Interactions, Identities, and Institutions*. Language in Society Ser. John Wiley & Sons Incorporated, Newark
- Ifenthaler D (2012) Determining the effectiveness of prompts for self-regulated learning in problem-solving scenarios. *Educational Technology & Society* 15:38–52
- Jung Y, Wise AF (2020) How and how well do students reflect? In: Rensing C (ed) *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Learning Analytics & Knowledge*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, United States, pp 595–604
- Khosrawi-Rad B, Rinn H, Schlimbach R, Gebbing P, Yang X, Lattemann C, Markgraf D, Robra-Bissantz S (2022) Conversational Agents in Education - A Systematic Literature Review. In: *European Conference on Information Systems*
- Knights S (1985) Reflection and Learning: the Importance of a Listener. In: Boud D, Keogh R, Walker D (eds) *Reflection: Turning experience into learning*, London, New York, pp 85–90
- Knipfer K, Kump B, Wessel D, Cress U (2013) Reflection as a catalyst for organisational learning. *Studies in Continuing Education* 35:30–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2012.683780>
- Kocielnik R, Hsieh G (2017a) Designing Reflective Dialogues on Self-Tracking Data. *CHI 2017 Workshop on Conversational UX Design*
- Kocielnik R, Hsieh G (2017b) Send Me a Different Message: Utilizing Cognitive Space to Create Engaging Message Triggers. In: *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing*, pp 2193–2207
- Kocielnik R, Hsieh G (2018) Facilitating Self-learning in Behavior Change Through Long-term Intelligent Conversational Assistance. In: Berkovsky S, Hijikata Y, Rekimoto J, Burnett M, Billinghamurst M, Quigley A

- (eds) *IUI 2018: Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces* : March 7-11, 2018, Tokyo, Japan. ACM Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, pp 683–684
- Kocielnik R, Avrahami D, Marlow J, Lu D, Hsieh G (2018a) Designing for Workplace Reflection: A Chat and Voice-Based Conversational Agent. *DIS '18 Proceedings of the 2018 Designing Interactive Systems Conference*:881–894. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3196709.3196784>
- Kocielnik R, Xiao L, Avrahami D, Hsieh G (2018b) Reflection Companion. *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies* 2:1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3214273>
- Kovanović V, Joksimović S, Mirriahi N, Blaine E, Gašević D, Siemens G, Dawson S (2018) Understand students' self-reflections through learning analytics. In: Pardo A, Bartimote-Aufflick K, Lynch G, Shum SB, Ferguson R, Merceron A, Ochoa X (eds) *LAK 18: Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Learning Analytics & Knowledge (LAK'18) : Towards User-Centred Learning Analytics* : March 5-9, 2018, Sydney, NSW, Australia. The Association for Computing Machinery, New York, New York, pp 389–398
- Krogstie BR, Prilla M, Wessel D, Knipfer K, Pammer V (2012) Computer Support for Reflective Learning in the Workplace: A Model. In: *2012 IEEE 12th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies*. IEEE, pp 151–153
- Krogstie BR, Prilla M, Pammer V (2013) Understanding and Supporting Reflective Learning Processes in the Workplace: The CSRL Model. In: Hernández-Leo D, Ley T, Klamma R, Harrer A (eds) *Scaling up Learning for Sustained Impact*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 151–164
- Kuhail MA, Alturki N, Alramlawi S, Alhejori K (2023) Interacting with educational chatbots: A systematic review. *Educ Inf Technol (Dordr)* 28:973–1018. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11177-3>
- Le DT, Nguyen C-T, Nguyen KA (2018) Dave the debater: a retrieval-based and generative argumentative dialogue agent. In: Slonim N, Aharonov R (eds) *Proceedings of the 5th Workshop on Argument Mining*. Association for Computational Linguistics, Stroudsburg, PA, USA, pp 121–130
- Lee Y, Kim TS, Kim S, Yun Y, Kim J (2023) DAPIE: Interactive Step-by-Step Explanatory Dialogues to Answer Children's Why and How Questions. In: Schmidt A, Väänänen K, Goyal T, Kristensson PO, Peters A, Mueller S, Williamson JR, Wilson ML (eds) *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–22
- Lin C-W, Lin M-J, Wen C-C, Chu S-Y (2016) A word-count approach to analyze linguistic patterns in the reflective writings of medical students. *Med Educ Online* 21:29522. <https://doi.org/10.3402/meo.v21.29522>
- Mauroux L, Könings KD, Zufferey JD, Gurtner J-L (2014) Mobile and Online Learning Journal: Effects on Apprentices' Reflection in Vocational Education and Training. *Vocations and Learning* 7:215–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-014-9113-0>
- McNamara DS, O'Reilly TP, Best RM, Ozuru Y (2006) Improving Adolescent Students' Reading Comprehension with Istart. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 34:147–171. <https://doi.org/10.2190/1RU5-HDTJ-A5C8-JVWE>
- McNamara DS, Graesser AC, McCarthy PM, Cai Z (2014) *Automated Evaluation of Text and Discourse with Coh-Metrix*. Cambridge University Press
- Mezirow J (1990) *Fostering critical reflection in adulthood: A guide to transformative and emancipatory learning*. The Jossey-Bass management series. Jossey-Bass Publishers, San Francisco
- Mirzababaei B, Pammer-Schindler V (2021) Developing a Conversational Agent's Capability to Identify Structural Wrongness in Arguments Based on Toulmin's Model of Arguments. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 4:645516. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2021.645516>
- Mirzababaei B, Pammer-Schindler V (2024) Facilitating the Learning Engineering Process for Educational Conversational Modules Using Transformer-Based Language Models. *IEEE Trans. Learning Technol.* 17:1222–1235. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2024.3367738>
- Mukherjee A, Santana VF de, Baria A (2023) ImpactBot: Chatbot Leveraging Language Models to Automate Feedback and Promote Critical Thinking Around Impact Statements. In: Schmidt A (ed) *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, United States, pp 1–8
- Nijholt A (2007) Conversational Agents and the Construction of Humorous Acts. In: Nishida T (ed) *Conversational informatics*. Wiley, Hoboken, N.J., pp 19–47
- Nye BD, Graesser AC, Hu X (2014) AutoTutor and Family: A Review of 17 Years of Natural Language Tutoring. *Int J Artif Intell Educ* 24:427–469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-014-0029-5>

- Olney AM, D’Mello S, Person N, Cade W, Hays P, Williams C, Lehman B, Graesser A (2012) Guru: A Computer Tutor That Models Expert Human Tutors. In: Cerri SA (ed) *Intelligent tutoring systems: 11th international conference, ITS 2012, Chania, Crete, Greece, June 14 - 18, 2012 ; proceedings*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 256–261
- Pammer-Schindler V, Prilla M (2021) The Reflection Object: An Activity-Theory Informed Concept for Designing for Reflection. *Interacting with Computers* 33:295–310. <https://doi.org/10.1093/iwc/iwab027>
- Pennebaker J, Francis M, Booth R (1999) Linguistic inquiry and word count (LIWC)
- Pintrich PR (2000) The Role of Goal Orientation in Self-Regulated Learning. In: Boekaerts M, Pintrich PR, Zeidner M (eds) *Handbook of Selfregulation*. Academic Press, London, pp 451–502
- Prilla M, Renner B (2014) Supporting Collaborative Reflection at Work. In: Goggins S, Jahnke I, McDonald DW, Bjørn P (eds) *Group '14: Proceedings of the 18th ACM International Conference on Supporting Group Work ; November 9 - 12, 2014, Sanibel Island, Florida, USA*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, pp 182–193
- Prilla M, Pammer V, Krogstie B (2013) Fostering Collaborative Redesign of Work Practice: Challenges for Tools Supporting Reflection at Work. In: Bertelsen OW, Ciolfi L, Grasso MA, Papadopoulos GA (eds) *ECSCW 2013: Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work, 21-25 September 2013, Paphos, Cyprus*. Springer London, London, pp 249–268
- Princeton University (2010) WordNet - A lexical database for the English language. <https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>. Accessed 4 September 2023
- Rainbird H, Fuller A, Munro A (eds) (2004) *Workplace learning in context*, 1st edn. Routledge, London
- Rakshit G, Bowden KK, Reed L, Misra A, Walker M (2019) Debbie, the Debate Bot of the Future. In: Eskenazi M, Devillers L, Mariani J (eds) *Advanced social interaction with agents: 8th International Workshop on Spoken Dialog Systems*, vol 510. Springer, Cham, pp 45–52
- Renner B, Prilla M, Cress U, Kimmerle J (2016) Effects of Prompting in Reflective Learning Tools: Findings from Experimental Field, Lab, and Online Studies. *Front Psychol* 7:820. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00820>
- Robe P, Kuttal SK (2022) Designing PairBuddy—A Conversational Agent for Pair Programming. *ACM Trans. Comput.-Hum. Interact.* 29:1–44. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3498326>
- Robert L. Hulsman, Jane van der Vloodt (2015) Self-evaluation and peer-feedback of medical students’ communication skills using a web-based video annotation system. Exploring content and specificity. *Patient Educ Couns* 98:356–363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2014.11.007>
- Roscoe RD, Allen LK, Weston JL, Crossley SA, McNamara DS (2014) The Writing Pal Intelligent Tutoring System: Usability Testing and Development. *Computers and Composition* 34:39–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compcom.2014.09.002>
- Ruan S, Jiang L, Xu J, Tham BJ-K, Qiu Z, Zhu Y, Elizabeth L. Murnane, Emma Brunskill, and James A. Landay (2019) QuizBot: A Dialogue-based Adaptive Learning System for Factual Knowledge. In: *CHI 2019, May 4-9, Glasgow, Scotland, UK*
- Ruan S, Jiang L, Xu Q, Liu Z, Davis GM, Brunskill E, Landay JA (2021) EnglishBot: An AI-Powered Conversational System for Second Language Learning. In: Hammond T, Verbert K, Parra D, Knijnenburg B, O’Donovan J, Teale P (eds) *26th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 434–444
- Rus V, Niraula N, Banjade R (2015) DeepTutor: An Effective, Online Intelligent Tutoring System That Promotes Deep Learning. *AAAI* 29. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v29i1.9269>
- Schön DA (1983) *The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action*. Basic Books, New York
- Schwendimann BA, Cattaneo AA, Dehler Zufferey J, Gurtner J-L, Bétrancourt M, Dillenbourg P (2015) The ‘Erfahrungsraum’: a pedagogical model for designing educational technologies in dual vocational systems. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training* 67:367–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2015.1061041>
- Shabrina P, Mostafavi B, Abdelshiheed M, Chi M, Barnes T (2023) Investigating the Impact of Backward Strategy Learning in a Logic Tutor: Aiding Subgoal Learning Towards Improved Problem Solving. *Int J Artif Intell Educ*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-023-00338-1>
- Shin H, Ko E-Y, Williams JJ, Kim J (2018) Understanding the Effect of In-Video Prompting on Learners and Instructors. In: Mandryk R, Hancock M, Perry M, Cox A (eds) *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–12

- Slovák P, Frauenberger C, Fitzpatrick G (2017) Reflective Practicum: A Framework of Sensitising Concepts to Design for Transformative Reflection. *Mindfulness and Reflection*, CHI 2017, May 6–11, Denver, CO, USA:2696–2707. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3025453.3025516>
- Solopova V, Rostom E, Cremer F, Gruszczynski A, Witte S, Zhang C, López FR, Plößl L, Hofmann F, Romeike R, Gläser-Zikuda M, Benzmüller C, Landgraf T (2023) PapagAI: Automated Feedback for Reflective Essays. In: Seipel D, Steen A (eds) *KI 2023: advances in artificial intelligence: 46th German conference on AI*, Berlin, Germany, September 26-29, 2023 : proceedings, vol 14236. Springer, Cham, pp 198–206
- Sriwisathiyakun K, Dhamanitayakul C (2022) Enhancing digital literacy with an intelligent conversational agent for senior citizens in Thailand. *Educ Inf Technol (Dordr)* 27:6251–6271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10862-z>
- Ullmann TD (2017) Reflective writing analytics: empirically determined keywords of written reflection. In: Wise A, Winne PH, Lynch G, Ochoa X, Molenaar I, Dawson S, Hatala M (eds) *Proceedings of the Seventh International Learning Analytics & Knowledge Conference*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 163–167
- Ullmann TD (2019) Automated Analysis of Reflection in Writing: Validating Machine Learning Approaches. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* 29:217–257. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-019-00174-2>
- van Dijk T (1977) *Text and Context: Explorations in the Semantics and Pragmatics of Discourse*. Longman Linguistics Library
- VanLehn K, Burlison W, Girard S, Chavez-Echeagaray ME, Gonzalez-Sanchez J, Hidalgo-Pontet Y, Zhang L (2014) The Affective Meta-Tutoring Project: Lessons Learned. In: Träüsan-Matu Ş (ed) *Intelligent tutoring systems: 12th international conference, ITS 2014, Honolulu, HI, USA, June 5 - 9, 2014 ; proceedings*, vol 8474. Springer, Cham, pp 84–93
- Wambsgans T, Kueng T, Soellner M, Leimeister JM (2021) ArgueTutor: An Adaptive Dialog-Based Learning System for Argumentation Skills. In: Kitamura Y, Quigley A, Isbister K, Igarashi T, Bjørn P, Drucker S (eds) *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–13
- Weizenbaum J (1966) ELIZA—a computer program for the study of natural language communication between man and machine. *Commun. ACM* 9:36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1145/365153.365168>
- Wild J, Pissarek M (2016) Ratte: Regensburger Analysetool für Texte. www.uni-regensburg.de/sprache-literatur-kultur/germanistik-did/ratte/index.html. Accessed 13 July 2021
- Williams JJ, Lombrozo T, Hsu A, Huber B, Kim J (2016) Revising Learner Misconceptions Without Feedback. In: Kaye J, Druin A, Lampe C, Morris D, Hourcade JP (eds) *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 470–474
- Winkler R, Hobert S, Salovaara A, Söllner M, Leimeister JM (2020) Sara, the Lecturer: Improving Learning in Online Education with a Scaffolding-Based Conversational Agent. In: Bernhaupt R (ed) *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, United States, pp 1–14
- Winne PH (2005) A Perspective on State-of-the-art Research on Self-regulated Learning. *Instructional Science* 33:559–565. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-005-1280-9>
- WKO (2021) *Lehrlingsstatistik: Hauptergebnisse der WKO-Lehrlingsstatistik*. <https://www.wko.at/service/zahlen-daten-fakten/daten-lehrlingsstatistik.html>. Accessed 25 October 2022
- Wolfbauer I, Pammer-Schindler V, Rose C (2020) Rebo Junior: Analysis of Dialogue Structure Quality for a Reflection Guidance Chatbot. In: Tom Broos, Tracie Farrell (eds) *Proceedings of the Impact Papers at EC-TEL 2020, co-located with the 15th European Conference on Technology-Enhanced Learning "Addressing global challenges and quality education" (EC-TEL 2020)*, Virtual, September 14-18, 2020, vol 2676. CEUR-WS.org
- Wolfbauer I, Pammer-Schindler V, Maitz K, Rose CP (2022) A Script for Conversational Reflection Guidance: A Field Study on Developing Reflection Competence with Apprentices. *IEEE Trans. Learning Technol.*:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2022.3207226>
- Wolfbauer I, Bangerl MM, Maitz K, Pammer-Schindler V (2023) Rebo at Work: Reflecting on Working, Learning, and Learning Goals with the Reflection Guidance Chatbot for Apprentices. In: *CHI EA '23: Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA

- Wollny S, Schneider J, Di Mitri D, Weidlich J, Rittberger M, Drachsler H (2021) Are We There Yet? - A Systematic Literature Review on Chatbots in Education. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 4:89. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2021.654924>
- Wong FK, Kember D, Chung LY, Yan L (1995) Assessing the level of student reflection from reflective journals. *J Adv Nurs* 22:48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.1995.22010048.x>
- Xu Y, Vigil V, Bustamante AS, Warschauer M (2022) “Elinor’s Talking to Me!”: Integrating Conversational AI into Children’s Narrative Science Programming. In: Barbosa S, Lampe C, Appert C, Shamma DA, Drucker S, Williamson J, Yatani K (eds) *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–16
- Xygykou A, Siriaraya P, Covaci A, Prigerson HG, Neimeyer R, Ang CS, She W-J (2023) The "Conversation" about Loss: Understanding How Chatbot Technology was Used in Supporting People in Grief. In: Schmidt A, Väänänen K, Goyal T, Kristensson PO, Peters A, Mueller S, Williamson JR, Wilson ML (eds) *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–15
- Zhang C, Schießl J, Plöbll L, Hofmann F, Gläser-Zikuda M (2023) Evaluating Reflective Writing in Pre-Service Teachers: The Potential of a Mixed-Methods Approach. *Education Sciences* 13:1213. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13121213>
- Zhu Q, Chau A, Cohn M, Liang K-H, Wang H-C, Zellou G, Yu Z (2022) Effects of Emotional Expressiveness on Voice Chatbot Interactions. In: Halvey M, Foster ME, Dalton J, Munteanu C, Trippas J (eds) *Proceedings of the 4th Conference on Conversational User Interfaces*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp 1–11
- Zimmerman BJ (2000) Attaining Self-Regulation. In: Boekaerts M, Pintrich PR, Zeidner M (eds) *Handbook of Selfregulation*. Academic Press, London, pp 13–39

Statements and Declarations

Funding

This work has partially been funded by the WKO; and within the Austrian COMET Program – Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies – under the auspices of the Austrian Federal Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology, the Austrian Federal Ministry of Economy, Family and Youth and by the State of Styria. COMET is managed by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG.

Competing interests

none

Appendix A – Feature analysis statistical calculations

A.1. Feature Analysis with Coh-Metrix

	GROUP	N	MEAN	STD.- DEVIATION	STD.- ERROR	MINIMUM	MAXIMUM
DESWC	00	10	6.9	3.213	1.016	4	13
	01	25	15.64	8.082	1.616	5	38
	10	7	17.14	5.21	1.969	9	23
	11	108	24.9	12.469	1.2	7	74
	Overall	150	21.79	12.375	1.01	4	74
DESSL	00	10	1.7583	0.776259	0.245475	1	3.25
	01	25	3.77	1.611079	0.322216	1.25	7
	10	7	4.51186	1.516378	0.573137	2.25	6.333
	11	108	5.93164	2.708016	0.260579	1.75	15.75
	Overall	150	5.22689	2.7131	0.221524	1	15.75
DESLD	00	10	1,0493	1,031159	0,326081	0	2,872
	01	25	2,33068	1,752804	0,350561	0	8,042
	10	7	3,10843	1,496794	0,565735	1,5	5,62
	11	108	3,41219	2,063913	0,1986	0,5	12,038
	Overall	150	3,06023	2,039342	0,166512	0	12,038
DESWLLTD	00	10	1,9045	0,933504	0,2952	0	3,545
	01	25	2,3008	0,45621	0,091242	1,326	3,028
	10	7	2,54929	0,390645	0,14765	2,036	2,927
	11	108	2,40317	0,441951	0,042527	1,104	3,766
	Overall	150	2,35968	0,500116	0,040834	0	3,766
LDMTLD	00	10	8.12	17.409106	5.505243	0	47.32
	01	25	58.33548	72.097799	14.41956	0	252
	10	7	42.64	24.997203	9.448054	0	74.06
	11	108	50.49977	40.684948	3.914911	0	224
	Overall	150	48.61361	46.899767	3.82935	0	252
SMCAUSVP	00	10	7.6923	24.325188	7.6923	0	76.923
	01	25	94.08576	78.79929	15.759858	0	285.714

	10	7	71.75057	51.710514	19.544737	0	142.857
	11	108	94.91443	59.602389	5.735243	0	263.158
	Overall	150	87.88053	64.658811	5.27937	0	285.714
SYNLE	00	10	0.025	0.079057	0.025	0	0.25
	01	25	0.63332	0.569478	0.113896	0	2.25
	10	7	0.19043	0.196659	0.07433	0	0.5
	11	108	0.78675	0.684478	0.065864	0	3.5
	Overall	150	0.68257	0.662791	0.054117	0	3.5
DRV P	00	10	74,2507	109,581843	34,652821	0	272,727
	01	25	253,5334	109,261495	21,852299	0	433,333
	10	7	196,02114	125,274488	47,349306	0	350
	11	108	248,50682	90,451399	8,70369	0	448,276
	Gesamt	150	235,27818	105,597775	8,622022	0	448,276
WRDVERB	00	10	81,0689	102,126311	32,295175	0	250
	01	25	178,9576	78,27622	15,655244	0	300
	10	7	112,71243	70,986096	26,830222	0	200
	11	108	165,35001	67,946711	6,538175	0	333,333
	Overall	150	159,54278	75,757724	6,185592	0	333,333
WRDPRO	00	10	24,359	55,539203	17,563038	0	166,667
	01	25	102,87312	75,614447	15,122889	0	272,727
	10	7	88,40614	96,892752	36,622018	0	285,714
	11	108	97,52575	60,714607	5,842266	0	277,778
	Overall	150	93,11361	66,939452	5,465583	0	285,714
WRDAOAC	00	10	47.7	150.840644	47.7	0	477
	01	25	179.95332	189.456397	37.891279	0	528
	10	7	128.47614	227.997825	86.175078	0	557
	11	108	239.41521	169.683083	16.327762	0	528
	Overall	150	211.54673	181.057659	14.783296	0	557

A.2. CohMetrix linguistic markers – ANOVA Values

METRIC	(I) GROUPID	(J) GROUPID		STD.- ERROR	SIGNIFICANCE	CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
--------	----------------	----------------	--	----------------	--------------	------------------------

			MEAN DIFFERENCE (I-J)			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
DESWC	00	01	-8,740	1,909	0	-13,9	-3,58
		10	-10,243	2,216	0,005	-17,13	-3,35
		11	-17,998	1,572	0	-22,19	-13,8
	01	00	8,740	1,909	0	3,58	13,9
		10	-1,503	2,548	0,934	-8,84	5,83
		11	-9,258	-9,258	0	-14,59	-3,92
	10	00	10,243	2,216	0,005	3,35	17,13
		01	1,503	2,548	0,934	-5,83	8,84
		11	-7,755	2,306	0,027	-14,68	-0,84
	11	00	17,998	1,572	0	13,8	22,19
		01	9,258	2,013	0	3,92	14,59
		10	7,755	2,306	0,027	0,84	14,68
DESSL	00	01	-2,011700	0,405069	0	-3,10997	-0,91343
		10	-2,753557	0,623493	0,009	-4,73801	-0,76911
		11	-4,173339	0,357993	0	-5,13652	-3,21016
	01	00	2,011700	0,405069	0	0,91343	3,10997
		10	-0,741857	0,657502	0,681	-2,7484	1,26469
		11	-2,161639	0,414396	0	-3,25674	-1,06654
	10	00	2,753557	0,623493	0,009	0,76911	4,73801
		01	0,741857	0,657502	0,681	-1,26469	2,7484
		11	-1,419782	0,629593	0,182	-3,39829	0,55873
	11	00	4,173339	0,357993	0	3,21016	5,13652
		01	2,161639	0,414396	0	1,06654	3,25674
		10	1,419782	0,629593	0,182	-0,55873	3,39829
DESLD	00	01	-1,28138	0,727896	0,392	-3,22162	0,65886
		10	-2,059129	0,958695	0,183	-4,61457	0,49632
		11	-2,362885	0,643035	0,002	-4,07692	-0,64885
	01	00	1,28138	0,727896	0,392	-0,65886	3,22162
		10	-0,777749	0,831881	0,923	-2,99516	1,43967
		11	-1,081505	0,431767	0,077	-2,2324	0,06939

	10	00	2,059129	0,958695	0,183	-0,49632	4,61457
		01	0,777749	0,831881	0,923	-1,43967	2,99516
		11	-0,303757	0,75874	0,999	-2,32621	1,7187
	11	00	2,362885	0,643035	0,002	0,64885	4,07692
		01	1,081505	0,431767	0,077	-0,06939	2,2324
		10	0,303757	0,75874	0,999	-1,7187	2,32621
DESWLLTD	00	01	-0,3963	0,182288	0,172	-0,8822	0,0896
		10	-0,644786	0,240087	0,047	-1,28475	-0,00482
		11	-0,498667	0,161036	0,014	-0,92791	-0,06942
	01	00	0,3963	0,182288	0,172	-0,0896	0,8822
		10	-0,248486	0,208329	0,796	-0,80379	0,30682
		11	-0,102367	0,108128	0,919	-0,39059	0,18585
	10	00	0,644786	0,240087	0,047	0,00482	1,28475
		01	0,248486	0,208329	0,796	-0,30682	0,80379
		11	0,146119	0,190012	0,969	-0,36037	0,6526
	11	00	0,498667	0,161036	0,014	0,06942	0,92791
		01	0,102367	0,108128	0,919	-0,18585	0,39059
		10	-0,146119	0,190012	0,969	-0,6526	0,36037
DESWLLTD	00	01	-0,3963	0,182288	0,172	-0,8822	0,0896
		10	-0,644786	0,240087	0,047	-1,28475	-0,00482
		11	-0,498667	0,161036	0,014	-0,92791	-0,06942
	01	00	0,3963	0,182288	0,172	-0,0896	0,8822
		10	-0,248486	0,208329	0,796	-0,80379	0,30682
		11	-0,102367	0,108128	0,919	-0,39059	0,18585
	10	00	0,644786	0,240087	0,047	0,00482	1,28475
		01	0,248486	0,208329	0,796	-0,30682	0,80379
		11	0,146119	0,190012	0,969	-0,36037	0,6526
	11	00	0,498667	0,161036	0,014	0,06942	0,92791
		01	0,102367	0,108128	0,919	-0,18585	0,39059
		10	-0,146119	0,190012	0,969	-0,6526	0,36037
LDMTLD	00	01	-50,215480	15,434747	0,014	-92,1990	-8,23191
		10	-34,520000	10,934964	0,043	-67,9754	-1,0646

		11	-42,379769	6,755311	0	-61,2895	-23,4699
	01	00	50,215480	15,434747	0,014	8,23191	92,19905
		10	15,69548	17,239183	0,799	-31,3499	62,74086
		11	7,835711	14,941561	0,952	-32,9926	48,66411
	10	00	34,520000	10,934964	0,043	1,0646	67,9754
		01	-15,69548	17,239183	0,799	-62,7408	31,3499
		11	-7,859769	10,227036	0,866	-40,4060	24,6865
	11	00	42,379769	6,755311	0	23,46997	61,28956
		01	-7,835711	14,941561	0,952	-48,6641	32,99269
		10	7,859769	10,227036	0,866	-24,6865	40,40604
SMCAUSVP	00	01	-86,393460	17,53695	0	-133,910	-38,87634
		10	-64,058271	21,004005	0,063	-131,563	3,44697
		11	-87,222126	9,595024	0	-113,942	-60,50223
	01	00	86,393460	17,53695	0	38,87634	133,91058
		10	22,335189	25,107168	0,81	-50,1562	94,82663
		11	-0,828666	16,770991	1	-46,3746	44,71733
	10	00	64,058271	21,004005	0,063	-3,44697	131,56351
		01	-22,335189	25,107168	0,81	-94,8266	50,15625
		11	-23,163854	20,368843	0,68	-90,3983	44,0706
	11	00	87,222126	9,595024	0	60,50223	113,94202
		01	0,828666	16,770991	1	-44,7173	46,37466
		10	23,163854	20,368843	0,68	-44,0706	90,39831
SYNLE	00	01	-0,60832	0,116607	0	-0,92804	-0,2886
		10	-0,165429	0,078422	0,235	-0,42156	0,09071
		11	-0,76175	0,070449	0	-0,94547	-0,57803
	01	00	0,60832	0,116607	0	0,2886	0,92804
		10	0,442891	0,136004	0,015	0,07178	0,814
		11	-0,15343	0,131568	0,651	-0,50548	0,19862
	10	00	0,165429	0,078422	0,235	-0,09071	0,42156
		01	-0,442891	0,136004	0,015	-0,814	-0,07178
		11	-0,596321	0,099313	0	-0,8763	-0,31635
	11	00	0,76175	0,070449	0	0,57803	0,94547

		01	0,15343	0,131568	0,651	-0,19862	0,50548
		10	0,596321	0,099313	0	0,31635	0,8763
DRVP	00	01	-179,282700	36,167717	0	-275,689	-82,87607
		10	-121,770443	47,635696	0,067	-248,745	5,20458
		11	-174,256124	31,951129	0	-259,423	-89,089
	01	00	179,282700	36,167717	0	82,87607	275,68933
		10	57,512257	41,334534	0,66	-52,6667	167,69126
		11	5,026576	21,453641	1	-52,1590	62,21219
	10	00	121,770443	47,635696	0,067	-5,20458	248,74547
		01	-57,512257	41,334534	0,66	-167,691	52,66675
		11	-52,485681	37,700325	0,659	-152,977	48,00618
	11	00	174,256124	31,951129	0	89,089	259,42325
		01	-5,026576	21,453641	1	-62,2121	52,15904
		10	52,485681	37,700325	0,659	-48,0061	152,97754
WRDVERB	00	01	-97,888700	27,086946	0,002	-170,090	-25,6872
		10	-31,643529	35,675615	0,94	-126,738	63,45138
		11	-84,281109	23,929033	0,003	-148,064	-20,4972
	01	00	97,888700	27,086946	0,002	25,68726	170,09014
		10	66,245171	30,95651	0,186	-16,2707	148,7611
		11	13,607591	16,067191	0,951	-29,2202	56,43539
	10	00	31,643529	35,675615	0,94	-63,4513	126,7384
		01	-66,245171	30,95651	0,186	-148,761	16,27076
		11	-52,637581	28,234757	0,326	-127,898	22,6234
	11	00	84,281109	23,929033	0,003	20,49723	148,0649
		01	-13,607591	16,067191	0,951	-56,4353	29,22021
		10	52,637581	28,234757	0,326	-22,6234	127,8985
WRDPRO	00	01	-78,514120	24,298919	0,009	-143,283	-13,74429
		10	-64,047143	32,003566	0,25	-149,354	21,25976
		11	-73,16675	21,466046	0,005	-130,385	-15,94807
	01	00	78,514120	24,298919	0,009	13,7442	143,28395
		10	14,466977	27,770193	0,996	-59,5556	88,48964
		11	5,34737	14,413414	0,999	-33,0722	43,76695

	10	00	64,047143	32,003566	0,25	-21,2597	149,35404
		01	-14,466977	27,770193	0,996	-88,4896	59,55568
		11	-9,119607	25,328587	0,999	-76,6340	58,39485
	11	0	73,166750	21,466046	0,005	15,9480	130,38543
		1	-5,34737	14,413414	0,999	-43,7669	33,07221
		10	9,119607	25,328587	0,999	-58,3948	76,63406
WRDAOAC	00	01	-132,25332	60,918298	0,164	-302,166	37,66014
		10	-80,776143	98,495858	0,844	-384,176	222,62457
		11	-191,715213	50,417118	0,013	-342,962	-40,46745
	01	00	132,25332	60,918298	0,164	-37,6601	302,16678
		10	51,477177	94,137628	0,945	-246,200	349,15516
		11	-59,461893	41,259482	0,483	-170,982	52,05919
	10	00	80,776143	98,495858	0,844	-222,624	384,17686
		01	-51,477177	94,137628	0,945	-349,155	246,2008
		11	-110,93907	87,708265	0,612	-408,128	186,25036
	11	00	191,715213	50,417118	0,013	40,46745	342,96297
		01	59,461893	41,259482	0,483	-52,0591	170,98298
		10	110,93907	87,708265	0,612	-186,250	408,1285

A.3 Feature Analysis with RATTE

	Group	N	Mean	Std.-Deviation	Std.-Error	Minimum	Maximum
gSmog	00	10	-0.017	1.76794	0.55907	-2	1.87
	01	25	1.5468	1.42665	0.28533	-2	3.48
	10	7	1.5243	2.06222	0.77945	-2	4.71
	11	108	2.8529	1.77002	0.17032	-2	6.66
	Overall	150	2.3819	1.90691	0.1557	-2	6.66
Disyllables	00	10	2	1.633	0.516	0	5
	01	25	4.2	3.175	0.635	0	14
	10	7	4.57	1.718	0.649	2	7
	11	108	6.19	3.732	0.359	0	18
	Overall	150	5.5	3.66	0.299	0	18
LexicalDensity	00	10	0.68471	0.1926639	0.0609257	0.25	1

	01	25	0.53248	0.137225	0.027445	0.2222	0.75
	10	7	0.585571	0.1132062	0.0427879	0.4	0.6923
	11	108	0.607719	0.0989921	0.0095255	0.2857	0.8
	Overall	150	0.599278	0.1188589	0.0097048	0.2222	1
Fillerwords	00	10	1.5	1.354	0.428	0	4
	01	25	2.4	1.555	0.311	0	5
	10	7	0.57	0.976	0.369	0	2
	11	108	3.21	2.158	0.208	0	13
	Overall	150	2.84	2.092	0.171	0	13
LIX	00	10	17.971	12.81406	4.05216	1	39.5
	01	25	23.556	13.18828	2.63766	1.25	58.89
	10	7	32.9829	13.61516	5.14605	14.77	51.31
	11	108	26.6875	9.21717	0.88692	1.75	55.5
	Overall	150	25.8783	10.69366	0.87313	1	58.89
RIX	00	10	1.156	0.34274	0.10838	0.74	1.74
	01	25	1.698	0.55438	0.11088	0.86	3.2
	10	7	1.6771	0.43542	0.16457	0.86	2.06
	11	108	2.3701	0.79928	0.07691	1.06	4.79
	Overall	150	2.1448	0.81803	0.06679	0.74	4.79
WordCount	00	10	6.6	2.98887	0.94516	4	12
	01	25	14.88	7.58463	1.51693	4	36
	10	7	14.7143	6.04743	2.28571	5	21
	11	108	24.1852	12.22923	1.17676	7	67
	Overall	150	21.02	12.16909	0.9936	4	67
AverageSentenceLength	00	10	1.95	1.01242	0.32016	1	4
	01	25	3.446	1.42616	0.28523	1	6
	10	7	3.6786	1.51186	0.57143	1.25	5.25
	11	108	5.7408	2.69409	0.25924	1.75	16.25
	Overall	150	5.0094	2.68385	0.21914	1	16.25
Types	00	10	6.1	3.315	1.048	1	11
	01	25	13.28	7.127	1.425	4	30
	10	7	13.71	6.525	2.466	5	22

	11	108	21.01	10.183	0.98	4	52
	Overall	150	18.39	10.273	0.839	1	52
Monosyllables	00	10	3.7	1.947	0.616	1	8
	01	25	8.64	4.415	0.883	2	17
	10	7	8	5.099	1.927	2	15
	11	108	14.15	7.512	0.723	3	41
	Overall	150	12.25	7.449	0.608	1	41
Trisyllables	00	10	0.9	0.876	0.277	0	2
	01	25	2.08	1.352	0.27	0	5
	10	7	2.14	1.952	0.738	0	6
	11	108	3.77	2.575	0.248	0	12
	Overall	150	3.22	2.471	0.202	0	12

A.4 RATTE linguistic markers – ANOVA Values

METRIC	(I) GROUPID	(J) GROUPID	MEAN DIFFERENCE (I-J)	STD.- ERROR	SIGNIFICANCE	CONFIDENCE INTERVAL	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
WORDCOUNT	00	01	-8,28000	1,78729	0	-13,1146	-3,4454
		10	-8,11429	2,47342	0,044	-16,0193	-0,2093
		11	-17,58519	1,50934	0	-21,6001	-13,5703
	01	00	8,28000	1,78729	0	3,4454	13,1146
		10	0,16571	2,74327	1	-7,9918	8,3232
		11	-9,30519	1,91985	0	-14,3861	-4,2242
	10	00	8,11429	2,47342	0,044	0,2093	16,0193
		01	-0,16571	2,74327	1	-8,3232	7,9918
		11	-9,47090	2,57085	0,02	-17,4013	-1,5405
	11	00	17,58519	1,50934	0	13,5703	21,6001
		01	9,30519	1,91985	0	4,2242	14,3861
		10	9,47090	2,57085	0,02	1,5405	17,4013

MONOSYLLABLES	00	01	-4,940	1,076	0	-7,85	-2,03
		10	-4,3	2,023	0,231	-10,94	2,34
		11	-10,448	0,949	0	-12,98	-7,91
	01	00	4,940	1,076	0	2,03	7,85
		10	0,64	2,12	0,99	-6,03	7,31
		11	-5,508	1,141	0	-8,52	-2,49
	10	00	4,3	2,023	0,231	-2,34	10,94
		01	-0,64	2,12	0,99	-7,31	6,03
		11	-6,148	2,058	0,069	-12,78	0,48
	11	00	10,448	0,949	0	7,91	12,98
		01	5,508	1,141	0	2,49	8,52
		10	6,148	2,058	0,069	-0,48	12,78
DISYLLABLES	00	01	-2,2	1,304	0,442	-5,68	1,28
		10	-2,571	1,718	0,581	-7,15	2,01
		11	-4,185	1,152	0,002	-7,26	-1,11
	01	00	2,2	1,304	0,442	-1,28	5,68
		10	-0,371	1,491	1	-4,34	3,6
		11	-1,985	0,774	0,066	-4,05	0,08
	10	00	2,571	1,718	0,581	-2,01	7,15
		01	0,371	1,491	1	-3,6	4,34
		11	-1,614	1,36	0,799	-5,24	2,01
	11	00	4,185	1,152	0,002	1,11	7,26
		01	1,985	0,774	0,066	-0,08	4,05
		10	1,614	1,36	0,799	-2,01	5,24
TRISYLLABLES	00	01	-1,180	0,387	0,025	-2,24	-0,12
		10	-1,243	0,788	0,443	-3,79	1,3
		11	-2,869	0,372	0	-3,88	-1,85
	01	00	1,180	0,387	0,025	0,12	2,24
		10	-0,063	0,786	1	-2,6	2,48
		11	-1,689	0,367	0	-2,65	-0,72
	10	00	1,243	0,788	0,443	-1,3	3,79
		01	0,063	0,786	1	-2,48	2,6

		11	-1,626	0,778	0,24	-4,16	0,91
	11	00	2,869	0,372	0	1,85	3,88
		01	1,689	0,367	0	0,72	2,65
		10	1,626	0,778	0,24	-0,91	4,16
AVERAGE- SENTENCE- LENGTH	00	01	-1,49600	0,42879	0,01	-2,681	-0,311
		10	-1,72857	0,655	0,099	-3,743	0,2858
		11	-3,79083	0,41195	0	-4,9279	-2,6538
	01	00	1,49600	0,42879	0,01	0,311	2,681
		10	-0,23257	0,63866	0,982	-2,2168	1,7516
		11	-2,29483	0,38544	0	-3,3095	-1,2802
	10	00	1,72857	0,655	0,099	-0,2858	3,743
		01	0,23257	0,63866	0,982	-1,7516	2,2168
		11	-2,06226	0,62748	0,04	-4,0348	-0,0898
	11	00	3,79083	0,41195	0	2,6538	4,9279
		01	2,29483	0,38544	0	1,2802	3,3095
		10	2,06226	0,62748	0,04	0,0898	4,0348
TYPES	00	01	-7,180	1,769	0,002	-11,97	-2,39
		10	-7,614	2,68	0,082	-16,15	0,92
		11	-14,909	1,435	0	-18,81	-11,01
	01	00	7,180	1,769	0,002	2,39	11,97
		10	-0,434	2,848	0,999	-9,09	8,22
		11	-7,729	1,73	0	-12,33	-3,13
	10	00	7,614	2,68	0,082	-0,92	16,15
		01	0,434	2,848	0,999	-8,22	9,09
		11	-7,295	2,654	0,095	-15,78	1,19
	11	00	14,909	1,435	0	11,01	18,81
		01	7,729	1,73	0	3,13	12,33
		10	7,295	2,654	0,095	-1,19	15,78
GSMOG	00	01	-1,5638	0,64787	0,097	-3,2907	0,1631
		10	-1,54129	0,85329	0,362	-3,8158	0,7332
		11	-2,86987	0,57234	0	-4,3955	-1,3443

	01	00	1,5638	0,64787	0,097	-0,1631	3,2907
		10	0,02251	0,74042	1	-1,9511	1,9961
		11	-1,30607	0,3843	0,005	-2,3304	-0,2817
	10	00	1,54129	0,85329	0,362	-0,7332	3,8158
		01	-0,02251	0,74042	1	-1,9961	1,9511
		11	-1,32858	0,67532	0,267	-3,1287	0,4715
	11	00	2,86987	0,57234	0	1,3443	4,3955
		01	1,30607	0,3843	0,005	0,2817	2,3304
		10	1,32858	0,67532	0,267	-0,4715	3,1287
RIX	00	01	-0,54200	0,15505	0,009	-0,9666	-0,1174
		10	-0,52114	0,19706	0,091	-1,1146	0,0723
		11	-1,21409	0,1329	0	-1,5862	-0,842
	01	00	0,54200	0,15505	0,009	0,1174	0,9666
		10	0,02086	0,19844	1	-0,5678	0,6096
		11	-0,67209	0,13494	0	-1,0307	-0,3135
	10	00	0,52114	0,19706	0,091	-0,0723	1,1146
		01	-0,02086	0,19844	1	-0,6096	0,5678
		11	-0,69295	0,18166	0,018	-1,2616	-0,1243
	11	00	1,21409	0,1329	0	0,842	1,5862
		01	0,67209	0,13494	0	0,3135	1,0307
		10	0,69295	0,18166	0,018	0,1243	1,2616

Appendix B - Heuristics and rules implemented in Rebo

Heuristic	Trigger	Dictionary	Rebo's turn - example
Rebo's empathetic statements			
Positive judgement	Expression of positive experience	positive	Great to hear!
Positive emotions	Expression of positive emotions	positive	It's great when you can have fun in your training!
Negative emotions	Expression of positive emotions	negative	I hope you have more fun next time!
Learning recognised	Expressions of learning insights	learning_planning	Very nice! :D
Planning recognised	Expression of planning insights	planning	Sounds like a plan!

Rebo's follow-up questions			
Negative judgement	Negative judgement of work outcome	negative	Oh no! What was the problem?
Fake judgment	Expression of having made an effort instead of self-assessment	fake_judgement	You've made an effort, that's great! Did you also complete your work according to the specifications?
Yes emotions	Expression of positive emotions without elaboration	yes	That's great! What was it that you liked best?
No emotions	Expression of negative emotions without elaboration	no	Oh no :/ Why didn't you enjoy it?
Yes learning	Affirming the learning question without elaboration	yes	Cool! What was it that you learned?
No learning	Negating the learning question without elaboration	no	Think again! Which skills did you improve doing this work?
Negative learning	Expression of not having learned anything	negative	What was new for you?
Fake learning - learning	Expression of having learned a lot	fake_learning1 "learning"	What was it specifically that you learned?
Fake learning - knowledge	Expression of having acquired knowledge	fake_learning2 "knowledge"	How could you expand your knowledge with this task?
No planning	Planning cannot be recognised	learning_planning	If you would perform the exact same task again tomorrow, what would be different?
Fake planning - precision	Planning on becoming more precise	fake_planning1 "precision"	Where do you need to pay more attention to precision?
Fake planning - measuring	Planning on paying attention to exact measurements	fake_planning2 "measure"	Which techniques could you apply to make your measures more exact?
Missing elaboration	5 words or less	-	Please explain this in more detail.

Appendix C - Rebo's scenario

```

<scenario default-language="en" scenario-name="rebo-example">
<configuration>
<!-- It *is* possible to hook up a LightSide classifier to TuTalk,
such that the predicted labels are treated as concepts.
but not today. -->
<!--
<module kind="model" name="animals"
classname="edu.cmu.cs.lti.tutalk.module.SidePredictor">
<param key="path" value="models/animals.ser" />
</module>

```

```

-->
</configuration>
<transitions>
<transition ack-type="agree" floor-status="neutral">
<tphrase>yes</tphrase>
<tphrase>okay</tphrase>
</transition>
<transition ack-type="none">
<tphrase>moving on...</tphrase>
</transition>
</transitions>
<!-- 'Concepts' define things that students might say,
      AND things that the tutor might say back.
      Tutor concepts should take the form of phrase lists.
      Student concepts can be phrase lists,
      regular expressions, or lists of annotations,
      but only one of these at a time. -->
<concepts>
<concept label="revisit">
<phrase>Über welche Aufgabe unterhalten wir uns heute?</phrase>
<phrase>Worüber willst du heute mit mir reflektieren?</phrase>
<phrase>Über welche Aufgabe möchtest du mit mir reflektieren?</phrase>
<phrase>Über welche Aufgabe willst du heute mit mir sprechen?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="description">
<phrase>Was hast du dabei so gemacht? Erkläre es mir mal Schritt für
Schritt.</phrase>
<phrase>Beschreib mir mal wie du bei dieser Arbeit vorgegangen
bist!</phrase>
<phrase>Erzähl mal: was hast du bei dieser Aufgabe alles so gemacht?
Schritt für Schritt ... </phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="judgement">
<phrase>Wenn du dir selber eine Schulnote 1-5 geben würdest, welche wäre es
und warum?</phrase>
<phrase>Wie gut erfüllt dein Ergebnis die gestellte Aufgabe?</phrase>
<phrase>Bist du mit dem Ergebnis deiner Arbeit zufrieden? Warum/Warum
nicht?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="positiveExp">
<phrase>Toll zu hören! | Was macht diese Aufgabe für dich interes-
sant?</phrase>
<phrase>Was hat dir dabei am besten gefallen?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="negativeExp">
<phrase>Oje! | Was war denn das Problem?</phrase>
<phrase>Was war denn das Problem?</phrase>
<phrase>Wobei hattest du die meisten Schwierigkeiten?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="negativExpAskFurther">
<phrase>Hat es trotzdem Spaß gemacht?| Erkläre mir, was dir gefallen hat
und was nicht!</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakeJudgement">
<phrase>Du hast dir also Mühe gegeben, sehr cool! | Hast du auch alles laut
Vorgaben umgesetzt? </phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="emotions">
<phrase>Hat dir diese Aufgabe Spaß gemacht? Warum / Warum nicht?</phrase>
<phrase>Wie hast du dich während der Durchführung dieser Arbeit ge-
fühlt?</phrase>

```

```

<phrase>Was hat dir besonders viel Spaß bei dieser Arbeit gemacht und was
nicht? Warum?</phrase>
<phrase>Worauf bist du bei der Lösung der Aufgabe besonders stolz?</phrase>
<phrase>Was hat dir an der Arbeit besonders gefallen und was nicht so
sehr?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="positiveEmotion">
<phrase>Hoffe, dass es dir weiterhin dabei so gut geht :)</phrase>
<phrase>Läuft bei dir :D</phrase>
<phrase>Es ist schon cool, wenn einem die Ausbildung Spaß macht!</phrase>
<phrase>Taugt mir, dass dir deine Ausbildung Spaß macht! :D</phrase>
-->
</concept>
<concept label="yesEmotionExp">
<phrase>Cool, dass es dir Spaß gemacht hat! Was hat dir denn daran gefal-
len?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="noEmotionExp">
<phrase>Schade :/ | Warum hat es dir denn nicht gefallen?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="negativeEmotionReaction">
<phrase>Das nächste Mal wird's bestimmt besser laufen!</phrase>
<phrase>Oje! Ich hoffe, die nächste Aufgabe liegt dir mehr</phrase>
<phrase>Bei der nächsten Aufgabe hast du hoffentlich mehr Spaß!</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="learning">
<phrase>Was hast du für dich aus dieser Arbeit gelernt?</phrase>
<phrase>Was konntest du von dieser Aufgabe mitnehmen?</phrase>
<phrase>Was würdest du sagen hast du durch diese Arbeit dazuge-
lernt?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="learningRecognized">
<phrase>Richtig nice! :D</phrase>
<phrase>Klingt sehr gut!</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="negativeLearningRecognized">
<phrase>Was war denn neu für dich?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakeLearning">
<phrase>Was hast du denn konkret dazu gelernt?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakeLearning2">
<phrase>Wo konntest du denn genau dein Wissen erweitern?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="yesLearningExp">
<phrase>Das freut mich! | Was hast du denn Neues gelernt?</phrase>
<phrase>Toll! | Wo konntest du denn dein Wissen erweitern?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="noLearningExp">
<phrase>Überleg noch mal | Welche Fähigkeiten hast du denn ein bisserl ver-
bessert?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="planning">
<phrase>Worauf wirst du beim nächsten Mal besonders achten, wenn du einen
ähnlichen Auftrag ausführst?</phrase>
<phrase>Wofür kannst du das Erlernte sonst noch anwenden?</phrase>
<phrase>Wo könntest du Teile dieser Arbeit in Zukunft wieder verwen-
den?</phrase>
<phrase>Was wirst du das nächste Mal besser machen?</phrase>
<phrase>Welche Fähigkeiten, die du hier geübt hast, wirst du in Zukunft
wieder brauchen?</phrase>

```

```

<phrase>Was wirst du beim nächsten Mal anders machen und was wirst du
gleich machen, wenn du eine ähnliche Aufgabe zu erledigen hast?</phrase>
<phrase>Wo kann man das in der Praxis sonst noch anwenden?</phrase>
-->
</concept>
<concept label="planningRecognized">
<phrase>Das klingt nach einem Plan!</phrase>
<phrase>Klingt gut!</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="noPlanningRecognized">
<phrase>Wenn du die gleichen Arbeitsschritte morgen nochmal machen würdest,
was würdest du dann anders machen als heute?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakePlanning">
<phrase>Was genau meinst du damit?</phrase>
<phrase>Wo möchtest du das nächste Mal genauer sein?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakePlanning2">
<phrase>Welche Techniken könntest du anwenden, damit deine Maße genauer
werden?</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fakeReflection">
<phrase>Wie genau meinst du das?</phrase>
<phrase>Ich glaube, du musst mir das etwas ausführlicher erklären
:)</phrase>
<phrase>Beschreibe das bitte ein wenig genauer.</phrase>
<phrase>Ich brauche da schon bisschen mehr Infos ;)</phrase>
<phrase>Etwas mehr Details wenn ich bitten darf ;)</phrase>
<phrase>Das ist mir bisschen zu wenig Info, erklär mir das doch bitte etwas
genauer!</phrase>
<phrase>Um zu verstehen, was du dir dabei denkst, brauche ich ein bisserl
mehr Text ;)</phrase>
<phrase>Erklär mir das bitte etwas genauer.</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="closing">
<phrase>Danke, dass du das mit mir besprochen hast!</phrase>
<phrase>Schön, dass wir uns unterhalten haben :)</phrase>
<phrase>Vielen Dank für deine Antworten!</phrase>
<phrase>Das war es schon wieder, vielen Dank für deine Antworten!</phrase>
<phrase>Super, danke fürs Mitmachen :)</phrase>
<phrase>Danke! Das war's für heute :D</phrase>
<phrase>Spitze, danke für deine Teilnahme!</phrase>
<phrase>Danke das war's für heute, viel Spaß bei deiner nächsten Auf-
gabe!</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="feedback">
<phrase>Das Gespräch war aus meiner Sicht</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="goodbye">
<phrase>Bis zum nächsten Mal :)</phrase>
<phrase>Schönen Tag noch und bis bald!</phrase>
<phrase>Danke und bis zum nächsten Mal ;)</phrase>
-->
<phrase>Schönen Tag noch :)</phrase>
<phrase>Danke, tschüss :)</phrase>
-->
</concept>
<!-- these match against external (MessageAnnotator) annotations. -->
<concept label="fake_yes_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>YES</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_no_annotation" type="annotation">

```

```

<phrase>NO</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="pos_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>POSITIVE</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="neg_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>NEGATIVE</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="planning_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>PLANNING</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_judgement_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>FAKE_JUDGEMENT</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_learning_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>FAKE_LEARNING</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_learning_annotation2" type="annotation">
<phrase>FAKE_LEARNING2</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_planning_annotation" type="annotation">
<phrase>FAKE_PLANNING</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_planning_annotation2" type="annotation">
<phrase>FAKE_PLANNING2</phrase>
</concept>
<concept label="fake_length" type="model"/>
<concept label="unanticipated-response">
<phrase>anything else</phrase>
</concept>
</concepts>
<!-- This is the meat of the hierarchical dialogue -
      one main goal with multiple steps, and subgoals that it may refer-
ence. -->
<script>
<goal name="start" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>revisit</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>description</initiation>
<response push="goalFakeDescriptionLength">fake_length</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>judgement</initiation>
<response push="goalPosJudgement">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegJudgement">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeJudgement">fake_judgement_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeJudgementLength">fake_length</response>
<response push="goalNeutralJudgement">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>learning</initiation>
<response push="goalYesLearning">fake_yes_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoLearning">fake_no_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeLearning">fake_learning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeLearning2">fake_learning_annotation2</response>
<response push="goalFakeLearningLength">fake_length</response>

```

```

<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>planning</initiation>
<response push="goalPlanning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoPlanningRecognized">unanticipated-response</response>
<response push="goalFakePlanning">fake_planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakePlanning2">fake_planning_annotation2</response>
<!-- delete this to avoid the fake-branch -->
<response push="goalFakePlanningLength">fake_length</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>closing</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>feedback</initiation>
</step>
<step>
<initiation>goodbye</initiation>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeDescriptionLength">
<step>
<initiation>fakeReflection</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<!-- Judgement reactions -->
<goal name="goalPosJudgement" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>positiveExp</initiation>
<response push="goalPosEmotions">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeEmotionsLength">fake_length</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNegJudgement" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>negativeExp</initiation>
<response push="goalNegJudgementAskFurther">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNegJudgementAskFurther">
<step>
<initiation>negativeExpAskFurther</initiation>
<response push="goalYesEmotions">fake_yes_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoEmotions">fake_no_annotation</response>
<response push="goalPosEmotions">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegEmotions">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeEmotionsLength">fake_length</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeJudgement" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeJudgement</initiation>
<response push="goalPosJudgement">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegJudgement">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNeutralJudgement">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>

```

```

</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeJudgementLength" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeReflection</initiation>
<response push="goalPosJudgement">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegJudgement">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNeutralJudgement">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<!-- Emotions reactions -->
<goal name="goalNeutralJudgement">
<step>
<initiation>emotions</initiation>
<response push="goalYesEmotions">fake_yes_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoEmotions">fake_no_annotation</response>
<response push="goalPosEmotions">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegEmotions">neg_annotation</response>
<response push="goalFakeEmotionsLength">fake_length</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalPosEmotions" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>positiveEmotion</initiation>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNegEmotions" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>negativeExp</initiation>
<response push="goalNegEmotionReaction">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalYesEmotions" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>yesEmotionExp</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNoEmotions" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>noEmotionExp</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNegEmotionReaction" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>negativeEmotionReaction</initiation>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeEmotionsLength" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeReflection</initiation>
<response push="goalYesEmotions">fake_yes_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoEmotions">fake_no_annotation</response>
<response push="goalPosEmotions">pos_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNegEmotions">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<!-- Learning reactions -->
<goal name="goalYesLearning" difficulty="1">
<step>

```

```

<initiation>yesLearningExp</initiation>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNoLearning" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>noLearningExp</initiation>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalLearning" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>learningRecognized</initiation>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalLearningNegativeResponse" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>negativeLearningRecognized</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeLearning" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeLearning</initiation>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeLearning2" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeLearning2</initiation>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakeLearningLength" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeReflection</initiation>
<response push="goalLearning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalLearningNegativeResponse">neg_annotation</response>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<!-- Planning reactions -->
<goal name="goalPlanning" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>planningRecognized</initiation>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalNoPlanningRecognized" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>noPlanningRecognized</initiation>
<response>unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakePlanning" difficulty="1">

```

```

<step>
<initiation>fakePlanning</initiation>
<response push="goalPlanning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoPlanningRecognized">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakePlanning2" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakePlanning2</initiation>
<response push="goalPlanning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoPlanningRecognized">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
<goal name="goalFakePlanningLength" difficulty="1">
<step>
<initiation>fakeReflection</initiation>
<response push="goalPlanning">planning_annotation</response>
<response push="goalNoPlanningRecognized">unanticipated-response</response>
</step>
</goal>
</script>
</scenario>

```

Appendix D - Rebo's dictionaries

C.1. Fake Judgement

bemüht

mühe

C.2. Fake learning 1 "learning"

vieles dazu gelernt

einiges dazu gelernt

vieles kennen gelernt

einiges kennen gelernt

neues gelernt

neues kennen gelernt

C.3. Fake learning 2 "Knowledge"

wissen

C.4. Fake planning 1 "precision"

genauigkeit

genau

genauer

C.5. Fake planning 2 „measure“

maße

masse

messen

C.6. Negative

Long list of words with negative meaning and/or connotations

C.7. No

nein

neein

nope

na

naa

nee

no

neiin

C.8. Learning - planning

Long list of words expressing learning, plans, and ambitions.

C.9. Positive

Long list of words with positive meaning and/or connotations and negated words with negative meaning and/or connotations.

C.10. Yes

ja

jap

jaaa

jaa

jawohl

Appendix E - Rebo's dialogue path

